

Ballot form for the revision of the ICSP Statutes

There are two ways to vote on the revision proposed below, only one of which must be chosen. The first option is to accept or reject all the proposed changes at once, or to abstain entirely. The second option is to vote for or against each block of related amendments separately, or to abstain from voting on that block. Each block is marked with a specific capital letter and background colour. The full text of the proposed amendments is given below, together with the block to which they belong.

Option 1: Vote on all changes at once

Please vote by putting an X in the space [] before the appropriate choice. Do not vote within Option 1 and also within Option 2.

Vote:

[] I ENDORSE THE ENTIRE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION

[] I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION

[] I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY

Option 2: Vote separately per block

Please vote by putting an X in the space [] before the appropriate choice. Do not vote within Option 2 and also within Option 1.

BLOCK E: Give IUMS Members Societies the right to appoint more than one Full Member to the ICSP, depending on their size.

Vote:

- I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK L: Give Life Members the same voting rights as Co-Opted Members.

Vote:

- I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK M: Miscellaneous clarifications, adaptations to modern practice, filling of gaps, and other improvements of the wording.

Vote:

- I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK P: Separation of powers between the legislative and judiciary branch, reduction of bureaucracy, and increase in fairness of procedures.

Vote:

- I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK
- I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK U: Formal regulation of the work of Ad Hoc Subcommittees in analogy to the work of Subcommittees on Taxonomy.

Vote:

I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK V: Clarification and streamlining of debates, revisions, and voting procedures.

Vote:

I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

BLOCK X: Extend the time that committed members can serve on the Executive Board and broaden the range of members who can serve as Members-At-Large.

Vote:

I ENDORSE THE NEWLY PROPOSED VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I VOTE TO RETAIN THE ENTIRE ORIGINAL (2019) VERSION OF THIS BLOCK

I ABSTAIN ENTIRELY REGARDING THIS BLOCK

The full text of the proposed revision

The first column of the table below indicates the block of interrelated amendments to which the texts in the second and third columns belong. The fourth column contains comments on the proposed amendments. **Yellow highlighting** is used to indicate the differences between the current text and the proposed new text.

Block	Current text	Proposed new version	Comments
-	STATUTES OF THE INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE ON SYSTEMATICS OF PROKARYOTES, ITS SUBCOMMITTEES AND THE JUDICIAL COMMISSION ON PROKARYOTE NOMENCLATURE OF THE BACTERIOLOGY AND APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY DIVISION OF THE IUMS	STATUTES OF THE INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE ON SYSTEMATICS OF PROKARYOTES, ITS SUBCOMMITTEES AND THE JUDICIAL COMMISSION ON PROKARYOTE NOMENCLATURE OF THE BACTERIOLOGY AND APPLIED MICROBIOLOGY DIVISION OF THE IUMS	
M	<p>Article 1</p> <p>Name. The name of the Committee shall be the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes of the Bacteriology and Applied Microbiology (BAM) Division of the International Union of Microbiological Societies (IUMS). For the purpose of abbreviation in all official documents it will be referred to as the ICSP.</p>	<p>Article 1</p> <p>Name. The name of the Committee shall be the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes of the Bacteriology and Applied Microbiology (BAM) Division of the International Union of Microbiological Societies (IUMS). For the purpose of abbreviation in all official documents, it will be referred to as the ICSP.</p>	
E	<p>Article 2</p> <p>Membership on the ICSP shall be Full Members, Co-opted Members and Life Members. Each Member Society (as defined in Article 3 of the constitution of the BAM Division of IUMS) of the BAM Division of the IUMS is entitled to appoint one Full Member to the Committee. The ICSP may co-opt other members and</p>	<p>Article 2</p> <p>Membership on the ICSP shall be Full Members, Co-opted Members and Life Members. Each Member Society (as defined in Article 3 of the constitution of the BAM Division of IUMS) of the BAM Division of the IUMS is entitled to appoint at least one delegate to act as a Full Member to the Committee. The ICSP may co-opt other members and</p>	

<p>appoint Life Members.</p> <p>(a) Full Members. Each Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS is entitled to appoint one Full Member to the ICSP by means of a letter to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP. Full Members may be appointed at any time. A Member Society is not obliged to appoint a member, and such positions will be considered to be vacant until a member is appointed.</p> <p>(1) The tenure of a Full Member is for one three year term. A term begins upon appointment by a Member Society and ends either upon appointment of another Full Member by the Member Society or on 1 April 2020, or every three years thereafter. Full Members shall be eligible for reappointment by his or her Member Society for an indefinite period.</p> <p>(2) When a Society ceases to be a member of the BAM Division of the IUMS, its appointed representative shall continue to be a Full Member until the end of his or her term.</p>	<p>appoint Life Members.</p> <p>(a) Full Members. Each Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS is entitled to appoint at least one Full Member to the ICSP by means of a letter to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP. Full Members may be appointed at any time. A Member Society is not obligated to appoint a member, and such positions will be considered to be vacant until a member is appointed.</p> <p>(1) The tenure of a Full Member is for one three-year term. A term begins upon appointment by a Member Society and ends either upon appointment of another Full Member by the Member Society or on 1 April 2020, or every three years thereafter. Full Members shall be eligible for reappointment by their Member Societies for an indefinite period.</p> <p>(2) When a Society ceases to be a member of the BAM Division of the IUMS, its appointed delegate(s) shall continue to be Full Members until the end of the term.</p> <p>(3) The number of Full Members that can be appointed as delegates to the ICSP by a Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS is dependent upon the number of members of the Member Society as follows: default, one delegate; 1-499 members, one delegate; 500-999 members, two delegates; >1000 members, three delegates.</p> <p>(4) For the purpose of appointing more than one delegate, a Member Society of the BAM Division of</p>	<p>Addition reflects changes to Article 2(a)(3) below.</p> <p>This amendment was approved in principle in ballot held in February 2023. A slightly different scaling compared to indicative range was cited on the ballot form. The change in scale is based on information regarding typical size of IUMS member societies.</p>
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		<p>the IUMS must provide evidence for the current number of its own members to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP prior to the appointment.</p> <p>(5) If the change in number of members of a Member Society affects the number of appointed delegates, all appointed delegates shall continue to be Full Members until the end of the term.</p>	
M	<p>(b) Co-opted Members. The ICSP may co-opt members for the purpose of assisting with the work of the Committee.</p> <p>(1) Proposals for co-opted membership must be submitted to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP and approved by a simple majority of the Full Members voting. Proposals should include a letter of nomination and two letters of support by Full Members.</p> <p>(2) The term of a Co-opted Member shall be the same as Full Members.</p> <p>3) Co-opted Members have the right to vote in all matters except the election of officers and co-opted members.</p>	<p>(b) Co-opted Members. The ICSP may co-opt members for the purpose of assisting with the work of the Committee.</p> <p>(1) Proposals for co-opted membership must be submitted to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP. Proposals must include a letter of nomination giving the case for co-option. The letter of nomination can be issued by any party, including self-nominations. All proposals must be supported in written form by at least two Full Members. Candidates must be approved by a vote of the Full Members [see Article 2(e)].</p> <p>(2) The tenure of a Co-opted Member is for one three-year term. A term begins upon appointment and ends on 1 May 2026, or every three years thereafter. If Co-opted Members wish to renew their membership, they should notify the Executive Secretary of the ICSP within two months before the start of a new term, so that a ballot can be arranged, and provide a brief justification for renewal.</p> <p>(3) Co-opted Members have the right to vote in all matters except the election of officers, Co-opted Members, and Life Members, and emendation of the</p>	<p>This opens up the process slightly as a means to encourage participation in the ICSP.</p> <p>This removes some ambiguity as to the type of majority needed. Similar edits made elsewhere for consistency.</p> <p>This streamlines the process of renewal, which helps preserve diversity of</p>

		ICSP Statutes	membership. As the new delegates of each term should vote to renew co-option, the term of co-opted members should end at a slightly later date.
L	(c) Life Members. The ICSP may appoint to Life Membership of the ICSP individuals who have rendered distinguished service to the ICSP. Such Life Members are not representatives of any Member Society. Life Members will not have a vote in the ICSP or be eligible for election to office and membership in the Executive Board.	(c) Life Members. The ICSP may appoint to Life Membership of the ICSP as many as five retired individuals who have rendered distinguished service to the ICSP. Life Members may not be the delegates of any Member Society (1) Proposals for Life Membership must be submitted by at least two Full Members to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP with an appropriate justification, and approved by a vote of the Full Members (see Article 2e). (2) Life Members have the right to vote in all ICSP matters except the election of officers, Co-opted Members and Life Members, and emendation of the ICSP Statutes. Life Members are not eligible for election to office and membership in the Executive Board.	Clarifies who can be appointed as a Life Member and sets an upper limit. Specifies the actual mechanism by which Life Members can be proposed. Slightly adapts it to the mechanism used for Co-Option. Gives Life Members voting rights similar to those of Co-Opted Members.
M	(d) Recognition of Alternates. If a Member of the ICSP cannot attend meetings of the ICSP, an Alternate having all the rights of a Member, except that of eligibility to office in the ICSP, will be appointed in accordance with the following provisions.	(d) Recognition of Alternates. If a Full Member of the ICSP cannot attend a meeting of the ICSP, an Alternate having all the rights of a Full Member, except that of eligibility to office in the ICSP, will be appointed in accordance with the following provisions.	The necessity to appoint alternates is mostly a hangover from the era in which voting was conducted at the plenary meeting (every 3-4 years), whereas

	<p>(1) The Member Society that the member represents shall have the right to appoint an Alternate from within its own society or from within any other Member Society.</p> <p>(2) If no appointment is made by the Member Society within two weeks of a request to appoint an Alternate, Full Members may appoint an Alternate from the Member Societies.</p> <p>(3) Notice of appointment of Alternates shall be made to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP.</p>	<p>(1) A Full Member of the ICSP who cannot attend the meeting shall have the right to appoint an Alternate from within the Full Member's own Member Society or, if this is not possible, from within any other Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS.</p> <p>(2) Notice of appointment of Alternates shall be made to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP prior to the meeting.</p>	<p>most voting is now by e-ballot ensuring delegate availability. Nevertheless, it may be desirable to ensure representation of a Member Society in a particular meeting and so this option is retained. The change simplifies the process by which alternates can be designated given that many/most Member Societies are happy for their delegates to act autonomously. The amendment also clarifies that an alternate is appointed for a specific meeting and not permanently. The members of the EB should not be included in the issue of alternates. If the Chair is absent from a meeting, it is clear that the Vice-Chair would take over the duties.</p>
<p>V</p>	<p>(e) Voting. Full and Co-opted Members are entitled to only one vote of the Committee. Decisions require a vote of at least ten Members and shall be reached on the basis of a majority of the members voting, including abstentions. In ballots the decision shall be based on the votes received within the allotted time period and not</p>	<p>(e) Voting. Members are entitled to one vote of the Committee. Decisions require a vote by a majority (i.e., more than 50%) of the members eligible to vote and shall be reached on the basis of a majority of those members who vote. The decision shall be based on the votes received within the allotted time period. All ballots should</p>	<p>While originally intended to clarify how voting is conducted, the proposal published in the IJSEM had actually changed the requirements from an</p>

	<p>on the number of members eligible to vote.</p>	<p>have abstention as an option. The standard voting period is six weeks.</p>	<p>absolute majority to a relative majority. The current Statutes require an absolute majority, as clear from the phrase “including abstentions”. In a relative majority, abstentions cannot count. This has been fixed. (See also https://www.britannica.com/topic/election-political-science/Plurality-and-majority-systems – plurality vs. majority). Assume the ICSP would use a plurality. With the quorum of ten, a decision could then be based on one vote in favour and nine abstentions. Not a good idea.</p> <p>The standard voting period is a change. It was selected after careful consideration of the expected absence times, such as holidays.</p>
-	<p>Article 3</p> <p>Functions of the ICSP</p> <p>(a) To represent the diversity of interests of different microbiological disciplines on matters concerning</p>	<p>Article 3</p> <p>Functions of the ICSP</p> <p>(a) To represent the diversity of interests of different microbiological disciplines on matters concerning the</p>	

	the nomenclature of prokaryotes.	nomenclature of prokaryotes.	
P	(b) To write , edit, interpret and disseminate the <i>International Code of Nomenclature for Prokaryotes</i> (ICNP). (1) To publish the ICNP.	(b) To study , edit and disseminate the <i>International Code of Nomenclature for Prokaryotes</i> (ICNP). Interpretations of the Code that underlie the preparation and publication of Opinions are a task assigned by the ICSP to its Judicial Commission [see Article 8]. (1) To publish the ICNP [see Article 13].	Change proposed to implement separation of powers between legislature (voting members) and judiciary (JC) and to reduce bureaucracy.
M	(c) To establish publications deemed necessary for advancement of the systematics of prokaryotes. (1) To maintain and disseminate the "Validation Lists" and the <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> . (2) To publish the <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology</i> (IJSEM). (d) To elect members of the Judicial Commission as vacancies occur and to replace the members of the several classes as their terms expire.	(c) To establish publications deemed necessary for advancement of the systematics of prokaryotes. (1) To maintain and disseminate the "Validation Lists" and the <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> [see Article 9]. (2) To oversee publication of the <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology</i> (IJSEM) [see Article 14]. (d) To elect members of the Judicial Commission as vacancies occur and to replace the members of the several classes as their terms expire.	Additions proposed here intend to better reflect the tasks of the ICSP and to clarify connections to other articles of the Statutes.
P	(e) To consider and vote upon all recommendations made by the Judicial Commission relating to Requests for Opinions. To consider and vote upon all recommendations communicated by the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP for emendation of the ICNP.	(e) To consider and vote upon all recommendations communicated by the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP for emendation of the ICNP [see Article 13].	Change proposed to implement separation of powers between legislature (voting members) and judiciary (JC) and to reduce bureaucracy.
M	(f) To receive reports of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy and ensure their dissemination. (g) To organize and sponsor regional, national or international conferences on the systematics of prokaryotes, either independently or in conjunction with meetings organized by other professional	(f) To receive reports of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy and ensure their dissemination [see Article 6]. (g) To organize and sponsor regional, national or international conferences on the systematics of prokaryotes, either independently or in conjunction with meetings organized by other professional	Additions proposed here intend to better reflect the tasks of the ICSP and to clarify connections to other articles of the Statutes.

	<p>societies. Conferences may be held electronically and made available via the Internet or other means as technology advances.</p> <p>(h) To elect the Executive Board (EB) of the ICSP and to authorize the EB-ICSP to perform such functions as are defined in the Statutes and such other functions as the ICSP may determine.</p> <p>(i) To appoint as Life Members of the ICSP individuals who have rendered distinguished service to the ICSP.</p> <p>(j) To take other actions that ensure the proper application of the Code.</p>	<p>societies. Conferences may be held electronically and made available via the Internet or other means as technology advances [see Article 4].</p> <p>(h) To elect the Executive Board (EB) of the ICSP and to authorize the EB-ICSP to perform such functions as are defined in the Statutes and such other functions as the ICSP may determine [see Article 5].</p> <p>(i) To vote on nominations of Co-opted Members of the ICSP [see Article 2(b)].</p> <p>(j) To appoint as Life Members of the ICSP individuals who have rendered distinguished service to the ICSP [see Article 2(c)].</p> <p>(k) To take other actions that ensure the proper application of the Code.</p>	
-	<p>Article 4</p> <p>Conduct of Business by the ICSP</p> <p>(a) The business of the ICSP will be conducted at Plenary Meetings or electronic forums. Plenary Meetings will be held at such times and places as may be determined by the EB-ICSP. When possible, Plenary Meetings shall be held at intervals of not more than three years and shall be held in association with other meetings, conferences, or congresses sponsored by the ICSP, IUMS, or other scientific societies.</p> <p>(b) All committees, subcommittees, and commissions of the ICSP have the authority to conduct business by electronic media.</p> <p>(c) When conducting the business of the ICSP in electronic media, the format of the meeting is</p>	<p>Article 4</p> <p>Conduct of Business by the ICSP</p> <p>(a) The business of the ICSP will be conducted at Plenary Meetings or electronic forums. Plenary Meetings will be held at such times and places as may be determined by the EB-ICSP. When possible, Plenary Meetings shall be held at intervals of not more than three years and shall be held in association with other meetings, conferences, or congresses sponsored by the ICSP, IUMS, or other scientific societies.</p> <p>(b) All committees, subcommittees, and commissions of the ICSP have the authority to conduct business by electronic media.</p> <p>(c) When conducting the business of the ICSP in electronic media, the format of the meeting is chosen by the</p>	

	<p>chosen by the Executive Board. Generally, time should be allowed for sharing the relevant materials on the topic under discussion, deliberations by the members, and voting.</p>	<p>Executive Board. Generally, time should be allowed for sharing the relevant materials on the topic under discussion, deliberations by the members, and voting.</p>	
M	<p>(d) The business of the ICSP will be conducted publicly, with minutes reported of all meetings of the ICSP and its committees. Minutes of the Plenary Meeting, Judicial Commission, Subcommittees on Taxonomy will be reported by publication in the IJSEM. Minutes of the EB-ICSP, editorial boards and other committees may be made publicly available by other means, including posting on a publicly accessible website or listserv, as determined by the committees.</p>	<p>(d) The business of the ICSP will be conducted publicly, with minutes reported of all meetings of the ICSP and its committees. Minutes of the Plenary Meeting will be reported by publication in the IJSEM. Minutes of the EB-ICSP, Judicial Commission, Subcommittees, editorial boards and other committees will be made publicly available by appropriate means, possibly including posting on a permanently publicly accessible website or repository, as determined by the committees.</p>	<p>The plenary is the main meeting of the ICSP and so those minutes should be published in IJSEM. However, it seems sufficient that routine minutes of the subsidiary components should be circulated by other means including email distribution, our own website and the 'ICSP community' within Zenodo (which also provides documents with a DOI). Opinions of the JC are considered separately below.</p>
X	<p>Article 5</p> <p>The Executive Board-ICSP. The membership of the Executive Board (EB) shall be: Chair and Vice-Chair, Executive Secretary, Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, Treasurer, and two other Full Members. The Chair, Vice-Chair, and Secretary of the Judicial Commission shall be ex officio non-voting members of the Executive Board. No single member may hold more than one function or cast more than one vote. No</p>	<p>Article 5</p> <p>The Executive Board-ICSP. The membership of the Executive Board (EB) shall be: Chair and Vice-Chair, Executive Secretary, Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, Treasurer, and two At-Large Members. The Chair, Vice-Chair, and Secretary of the Judicial Commission shall be ex officio non-voting members of the Executive Board. No single member may hold more than one function or cast more than one vote. No member of the EB-ICSP</p>	

	<p>member of the EB-ICSP may serve on the Executive Board for more than two consecutive terms in any capacity.</p> <p>(a) Election of the Executive Board. The terms of office for members of the EB-ICSP will begin on September 1, 2020, and every three years thereafter. One term is for three years. Members of the EB who are Full Members or Co-opted Members at the beginning of their term will retain their membership status until the end of their term even if their Member Society appoints another Member. The Chair and Vice-Chair will be elected from the Full Members. The Executive Secretary, the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, and the Treasurer will be elected from the Full or Co-opted Members.</p>	<p>may serve on the Executive Board in any capacity for more than three consecutive terms, or in the same capacity for more than two consecutive terms. After an absence of one term, former members of the EB-ICSP who have served three consecutive terms shall be eligible for re-election as an Officer on the Executive Board.</p> <p>(a) Election of the Executive Board. The terms of office for members of the EB-ICSP begin on September 1, 2020, and every three years thereafter. One term is for three years. Members of the EB who are Full Members or Co-opted Members at the beginning of their term will retain their membership status until the end of their term, even if their Member Society appoints another delegate for the next term or the co-option is not renewed. The Chair and Vice-Chair will be elected from the Full Members. The Executive Secretary, the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, the Treasurer and two At-Large Members will be elected from the Full and Co-opted Members.</p>	<p>It was agreed to propose this clarification at the April 2023 meeting of the Executive Board. However, not all circulated ideas, including some ideas for changes, could be considered at that time. The revised version of the proposal is a compromise between the discussed ideas.</p> <p>Addition to better reflect the situation of co-opted members. As Member Societies cannot appoint an arbitrary number of delegates, the appointment of another delegate must refer to the next term.</p>
M	<p>(b) Functions of the EB-ICSP</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) To organize meetings and electronic forums of the ICSP plenary and prepare and publish agenda for such meetings and forums. (2) To conduct the business of the ICSP between plenary meetings as directed by the ICSP. (3) To organize regional, national and international conferences and symposia on the systematics of prokaryotes. 	<p>(b) Functions of the EB-ICSP</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) To organize meetings and electronic forums of the ICSP plenary [see Article 4(a)]. (2) To conduct the business of the ICSP between plenary meetings as directed by the ICSP [see Article 4(b)]. (3) To organize regional, national and international conferences and symposia on the systematics of prokaryotes or other appropriate topics. 	<p>Additions proposed here intend to better reflect the tasks of the EB-ICSP and to clarify connections to other articles of the Statutes.</p>
U	<p>(4) To appoint Subcommittees on Taxonomy, either on its own initiative or at the request of others,</p>	<p>(4) To appoint Subcommittees [see Article 6], either on its own initiative or at the request of others, and to</p>	<p>Change in agreement with the one proposed below,</p>

	<p>and to facilitate meetings of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy at the plenary meetings of the ICSP or elsewhere.</p>	<p>facilitate meetings of the Subcommittees at the plenary meetings of the ICSP or elsewhere.</p>	<p>using “Subcommittee” to collectively refer to Subcommittees on Taxonomy and Ad Hoc Subcommittees.</p>
<p>M</p>	<p>(5) To provide for the initial appointment and subsequent election of Chairs and Secretaries of Subcommittees on Taxonomy.</p> <p>(6) To deal with such business as the Judicial Commission may from time to time request.</p> <p>(7) To recommend to the ICSP the establishment of any Committees that are deemed necessary for the work and functioning of the ICSP and to consider recommendations submitted to it by those committees.</p> <p>(8) Upon approval of the ICSP to:</p> <p>(a) establish publications authorized by the ICSP</p> <p>(b) negotiate such contracts as may be necessary for the issuance of publications authorized by the ICSP</p> <p>(c) establish such Trusts or enter into such agreements as may be advisable for the auditing and administration of funds that may be designated for the payment of the necessary operating expenses of the ICSP and its subordinate agencies, whether such funds originate from grants, gifts, royalties, the sale of</p>	<p>(5) To provide for the initial appointment and subsequent election of Chairs and Secretaries of Subcommittees on Taxonomy [see Article 6].</p> <p>(6) To deal with such business as the Judicial Commission may request [see Article 7].</p> <p>(7) To recommend to the ICSP the establishment of any Committees that are deemed necessary for the work and functioning of the ICSP and to consider recommendations submitted to it by those committees.</p> <p>(8) To appoint or replace individuals to implement and keep up-to-date the representation of the ICSP on electronic media, such as websites or social media, as deemed appropriate for the purposes of the ICSP.</p> <p>(9) Upon approval of the ICSP to:</p> <p>(a) establish publications authorized by the ICSP [see Articles 9 and 14].</p> <p>(b) negotiate such contracts as may be necessary for the issuance of publications authorized by the ICSP.</p> <p>(c) establish such Trusts or enter into such agreements as may be advisable for the auditing and administration of funds that may be designated for the payment of the necessary operating expenses of the ICSP and its subordinate agencies, whether such funds originate from grants, gifts, royalties, the sale of publications or</p>	<p>Change intended to clarify that the ICSP should be active in electronic media.</p>

	<p>publications or other sources.</p> <p>(d) To request from appropriate agencies grants for the necessary expenses of the ICSP and its subordinate agencies.</p> <p>(9) To ensure the proper functioning of the organizations and officers of the ICSP.</p> <p>(10) To perform such other functions enumerated in the Statutes or assigned to it by the ICSP.</p>	<p>other sources.</p> <p>(d) request from appropriate agencies grants for the necessary expenses of the ICSP and its subordinate agencies.</p> <p>(10) To ensure the proper functioning of the organizations and officers of the ICSP.</p> <p>(11) To perform such other functions enumerated in the Statutes or assigned to it by the ICSP.</p>	
M	<p>(c) Duties of the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP. In addition to the duties specified below, the Chair and Vice-Chair shall be ex officio, but non-voting, members of all Committees, Commissions and Subcommittees of the ICSP, unless otherwise stated.</p> <p>(1) Duties of the Chair of the ICSP are:</p> <p>(a) To preside at meetings of the ICSP and its Executive Board.</p> <p>(b) With the other members of the Executive Board, to prepare the agenda for meetings of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(c) With the other members of the Executive Board, to prepare the agenda for meetings and forums of the ICSP.</p> <p>(d) To serve on the Publications Committee.</p> <p>(e) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP.</p> <p>(f) To assume such duties as may be requested by the ICSP or determined by the functions of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(2) Duties of the Vice-Chair are:</p> <p>(a) To preside at the meetings of the ICSP and EB-ICSP in the absence of the Chair.</p>	<p>(c) Duties of the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP. In addition to the duties specified below, the Chair and Vice-Chair shall be ex officio, but non-voting, members of all Committees, Commissions and Subcommittees of the ICSP, unless otherwise stated.</p> <p>(1) Duties of the Chair of the ICSP are:</p> <p>(a) To preside at meetings of the ICSP and its Executive Board [see Article 4].</p> <p>(b) With the other members of the Executive Board, to prepare the agenda for meetings of the EB-ICSP [see Article 4(d)].</p> <p>(c) With the other members of the Executive Board, to prepare the agenda for meetings and forums of the ICSP [see Article 4(a)].</p> <p>(d) To serve on the Publications Committee [see Article 9].</p> <p>(e) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP [see Article 13].</p> <p>(f) To assume such duties as may be requested by the ICSP or determined by the functions of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(2) Duties of the Vice-Chair are:</p> <p>(a) To preside at the meetings of the ICSP and EB-ICSP in the absence of the Chair [see Article 4(d)].</p>	<p>Additions proposed here intend to clarify connections to other articles of the Statutes.</p>

	<p>(b) With the other members of the Executive Board to prepare the agenda for the meetings and forums of the ICSP.</p> <p>(c) To assume such duties as may be requested by the ICSP or determined by the functions of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(d) To chair the Publications Committee.</p> <p>(e) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP and IJSEM.</p>	<p>(b) With the other members of the Executive Board, to prepare the agenda for the meetings and forums of the ICSP [see Article 4(a)].</p> <p>(c) To assume such duties as may be requested by the ICSP or determined by the functions of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(d) To chair the Publications Committee [see Article 9].</p> <p>(e) To serve on the Editorial Boards for the ICNP and IJSEM [see Articles 13 and 14].</p>	
M	<p>(d) Duties of the Executive Secretary. In addition to the duties specified below, the Executive Secretary shall be responsible to the Executive Board in all matters associated with communications between the ICSP and the Executive Board of the IUMS, Division Council of BAM and Member Societies. The Executive Secretary shall perform the following duties:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Be Secretary of the EB-ICSP and the ICSP and submit the minutes of the plenary meetings for publication in the IJSEM. (2) Be secretary to the electronic meetings of the EB-ICSP and ICSP and report the minutes in an appropriate manner as determined by the plenary of the ICSP or, in the absence of specific instructions, by the EB-ICSP. (3) With the other members of the EB-ICSP, to prepare the agenda for meetings of the EBICSP. (4) Prepare, in cooperation with other members of the EB-ICSP, the agenda for meetings and forums of the ICSP. 	<p>(d) Duties of the Executive Secretary. In addition to the duties specified below, the Executive Secretary shall be responsible to the Executive Board in all matters associated with communications between the ICSP and the Executive Board of the IUMS, Division Council of BAM and Member Societies. The Executive Secretary shall perform the following duties:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Be Secretary of the EB-ICSP and the ICSP and submit the minutes of the plenary meetings for publication in the IJSEM [see Article 4(a)]. (2) Be secretary to the electronic meetings of the EB-ICSP and ICSP and report the minutes in an appropriate manner, as determined by the plenary of the ICSP or, in the absence of specific instructions, by the EB-ICSP [see Article 4(d)]. (3) With the other members of the EB-ICSP, to prepare the agenda for meetings of the EB-ICSP [see Article 4(d)]. (4) Prepare, in cooperation with other members of the EB-ICSP, the agenda for meetings and forums of the ICSP [see Article 4(a)]. 	<p>Additions proposed here intend to clarify connections to other articles of the Statutes.</p>

<p>(5) Request nominations from Member Societies for Full Members to the ICSP. Receive nominations for appointment of Full, Co-opted and Life Members and transmit these to the EBICSP.</p> <p>(6) Receive nominations for alternates for meetings of the ICSP in accordance with Article 2d.</p> <p>(7) Transmit to the ICSP such recommendations from the Judicial Commission as may require action by the ICSP.</p> <p>(8) If the members are asked to vote upon any proposal, to tabulate and announce the result of the ballot and to certify the result to the Chair of the ICSP and to the Chair of the Judicial Commission.</p> <p>(9) Prepare every three years a complete list of all members and officers of the ICSP and the Judicial Commission and forward these to the Secretary Treasurer of the BAM Division of IUMS and the Chair of the ICSP.</p> <p>(10) Present every three years a report covering all pertinent actions of the ICSP and the Judicial Commission and other committees of the ICSP to the plenary of the ICSP and the Secretary of the BAM Division of the IUMS.</p> <p>(11) To maintain an archive of the important documents of the ICSP, including names and affiliations of its members and officers, minutes of meetings, copies of contracts, correspondence regarding any prizes awarded by the ICSP, reports of the treasurer, and</p>	<p>(5) Request nominations from Member Societies for Full Members to the ICSP. Receive nominations for appointment of Full, Co-opted and Life Members and transmit these to the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(6) Receive nominations for alternates for meetings of the ICSP in accordance with Article 2d.</p> <p>(7) Transmit to the ICSP such recommendations from the Judicial Commission as may require action by the ICSP [see Article 7(a)].</p> <p>(8) If the members are asked to vote upon any proposal, to tabulate and announce the result of the ballot and to certify the result to the Chair of the ICSP and to the Chair of the Judicial Commission.</p> <p>(9) Prepare every three years a complete list of all members and officers of the ICSP and the Judicial Commission and forward these to the Secretary Treasurer of the BAM Division of IUMS and the Chair of the ICSP.</p> <p>(10) Present every three years a report covering all pertinent actions of the ICSP and the Judicial Commission and other committees of the ICSP to the plenary of the ICSP and the Secretary of the BAM Division of the IUMS.</p> <p>(11) To maintain an archive of the important documents of the ICSP, including names and affiliations of its members and officers, minutes of meetings, copies of contracts, correspondence regarding any prizes awarded by the ICSP, reports</p>	<p>Change in agreement with the one proposed below, using the term "Subcommittee" to</p>
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	documents related to ad hoc committees. (12) Perform such duties as the EB-ICSP may from time to time determine.	of the treasurer, and documents related to Ad Hoc Subcommittees. (12) Perform such duties as the EB-ICSP may from time to time determine.	collectively refer to Subcommittees on Taxonomy and Ad Hoc Subcommittees.
M	(e) Duties of the Treasurer. The Treasurer shall receive funds which may be made available to the ICSP from any source and distribute them as directed by the EBICSP or its Chair. (1) Checks or requests for electronic fund transfers issued by the Treasurer shall bear the Treasurer's signature but must have been authorized in writing by the Chair of the ICSP, the Vice-Chair of the ICSP or the Chair of the Judicial Commission. (2) A statement of accounts shall be furnished by the Treasurer to the EB-ICSP before September 1 of each year. In addition, a statement will be furnished to the ICSP at each Plenary Meeting of the ICSP and to the Secretary Treasurer of the BAM Division of the IUMS as requested.	(e) Duties of the Treasurer. The Treasurer shall receive funds which may be made available to the ICSP from any source and distribute them as directed by the EB-ICSP or its Chair. (1) Checks or requests for electronic fund transfers issued by the Treasurer shall bear the Treasurer's signature but must have been authorized in writing by the Chair of the ICSP or the Vice-Chair of the ICSP. (2) A statement of accounts shall be furnished by the Treasurer to the EB-ICSP before September 1 of each year. In addition, a statement will be furnished to the ICSP at each Plenary Meeting of the ICSP and to the Secretary Treasurer of the BAM Division of the IUMS as requested.	This change better reflects current practice.
M	(f) Duties of the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be responsible to the Executive Board for all matters associated with the Subcommittees on Taxonomy of the ICSP. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall perform the following duties: (1) Prepare, in cooperation with the Chair of the ICSP and the Executive Secretary, the agenda for meetings of the EB-ICSP.	(f) Duties of the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be responsible to the Executive Board for all matters associated with the Subcommittees of the ICSP. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall perform the following duties:	Adaptation proposed in agreement with the new Article 6. The title of the office itself has been kept. Deletion in agreement with the one proposed below, using the term "Subcommittee" to collectively refer to Subcommittees on Taxonomy and Ad Hoc

	<p>(2) Prepare, in cooperation with other members of the EB-ICSP, the agenda for meetings and forums of the ICSP.</p> <p>(3) Serve as a non-voting member of each Subcommittee on Taxonomy.</p> <p>(4) Act as a liaison between the officers of the Subcommittees on Taxonomy and the ICSP, transmitting requests and recommendations to the EB-ICSP or Judicial Commission, whichever is appropriate.</p>	<p>(1) Serve as a non-voting member of each Subcommittee [see Article 6].</p> <p>(2) Act as a liaison between the officers of the Subcommittees and the ICSP, transmitting requests and recommendations to the EB-ICSP and/or Judicial Commission, whichever is appropriate.</p> <p>(3) Organise, where needed, meetings of the officers of the Subcommittees, using electronic forums, to discuss overarching matters.</p>	<p>Subcommittees.</p> <p>These are the duties of the Chair and Vice Chair in conjunction “with the other members of the Executive Board”, as described above (article 5.c.1). Hence can be deleted here for simplicity.</p> <p>A recent meeting of this type was held in October 2022 and considered useful; hence, this activity is formalized here.</p>
<p>U</p>	<p>Article 6</p> <p>Organization and Functions of Subcommittees on Taxonomy</p> <p>The formation of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy may be proposed by an individual, a group of individuals or the EBICSP. A proposal must be accompanied by a description of the taxa to be studied, the reasons therefore, and a list of proposed subcommittee members. Such proposals shall be submitted to the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy for approval by the EB-ICSP. Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall work under the following rules:</p>	<p>Article 6</p> <p>Organization and Functions of Subcommittees on Taxonomy and Ad Hoc Subcommittees</p> <p>The formation of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy or an Ad Hoc Subcommittee may be proposed by an individual, a group of individuals or the EB-ICSP. A proposal must be accompanied by a description of the prokaryotic taxa or, alternatively, the overarching nomenclature-related topic to be studied, the reasons therefore, and a list of proposed Subcommittee members. Such proposals shall be submitted to the Secretary for Subcommittees for approval by the EB-ICSP. Subcommittees shall work under the following rules:</p>	<p>The ICSP has used ad hoc committees (and working groups) in the past. The additions here serve to formalise the status of these.</p> <p>We have suggested here that ad hoc committees be called "Ad Hoc Subcommittees" to emphasize their position within the ICSP. The term "Subcommittee" can then be used to refer collectively to the Taxonomy Subcommittee and the Ad Hoc Subcommittees.</p>

<p>M</p>	<p>(a) Upon formation of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy, the members will elect a Chair and Secretary and report their names to the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. The terms of the officers of the subcommittees begin on 1 September 2020, and every three years thereafter. However, they may be re-elected, and there is no term limit. The functions of the Chair are to organize with the Secretary meetings of the Subcommittee, chair such meetings, and coordinate all business as necessary with the ICSP and the Judicial Commission. The functions of the Secretary are to assist the Chair in organizing the subcommittee meetings, prepare minutes of the meetings for publication in the IJSEM, and maintain a list of the members of the Subcommittee.</p> <p>(b) Regular members of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy shall be affiliated with an IUMS member society. The subcommittee may co-opt other specialists, but co-opted members have no voting rights in the administrative workings of the subcommittee. New members may be elected to a Subcommittee on Taxonomy at any time by a vote of the existing regular members.</p> <p>(1) The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be a non-voting member of each Subcommittee on Taxonomy and acts as liaison between each Subcommittee on Taxonomy, the EB-ICSP, the ICSP and the Judicial Commission.</p>	<p>(a) Upon formation of a Subcommittee, the members will elect a Chair and Secretary and report their names to the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. The terms of the officers of the subcommittees begin on 1 September 2020, and every three years thereafter. However, they may be re-elected, and there are no term limits. The functions of the Chair are to organize, with the Secretary, meetings of the Subcommittee, chair such meetings, and coordinate all business as necessary with the ICSP and the Judicial Commission. The functions of the Secretary are to assist the Chair in organizing the Subcommittee meetings, prepare minutes of the meetings for publication [see Article 4(d)] and maintain a list of the members of the Subcommittee.</p> <p>(b) A Subcommittee shall contain at least one regular member, which is affiliated with a Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS. The Subcommittee may co-opt other specialists. New members may be elected to a Subcommittee at any time. Prior to the election of officers [see Article 6(a)], the regular members of the Subcommittee shall decide, for the entire term, whether only regular members or also co-opted members of the Subcommittee shall be eligible for office and have the right to vote in the election of new members and officers.</p> <p>(1) The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be a non-voting member of each Subcommittee and act as liaison between each Subcommittee, the EB-ICSP, the ICSP and the Judicial Commission.</p>	<p>Simplification intended to give the Subcommittees more flexibility.</p> <p>The further addition solves a logical inconsistency. For Article 6(b) the IJSEM paper suggested to delete the phrase “but co-opted members have no voting rights in the administrative workings of the Subcommittee”. The intention of this removal is clear. However, the sentence “New members may be</p>
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	<p>(2) Members who cannot attend meetings of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy may designate an Alternate in a letter to the Subcommittee's secretary. The designated Alternate may vote on the member's behalf. However, no member or alternate of the subcommittee may cast more than one vote.</p> <p>(3) There is no term limit on membership in a Subcommittee on Taxonomy, but all members should be actively engaged in the work of the subcommittee. Members who resign or who have ceased to interest themselves in the work of the subcommittee shall be removed from the membership roster by a majority vote of the Subcommittee.</p> <p>(4) Each Subcommittee on Taxonomy is encouraged to meet at least once every three years at any location considered appropriate by the subcommittee's members or hold electronic forums. Meetings and forums should be coordinated with the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. A portion of the meeting may be restricted to regular members of the subcommittee or their alternates in order to deal, inter alia, with changes of membership and election of officers.</p>	<p>(2) Members who cannot attend meetings of a Subcommittee may designate an Alternate in a letter to the Subcommittee's secretary. The designated Alternate may vote on the member's behalf. However, no member or alternate of the subcommittee may cast more than one vote.</p> <p>(3) There is no term limit on membership in a Subcommittee, but all members should be actively engaged in the work of the Subcommittee. Members who cease to have interest in the work of the Subcommittee shall resign or be removed from the membership roster by a vote of the members of the Subcommittee.</p> <p>(4) Each Subcommittee is encouraged to meet at least once every year at any location considered appropriate by the Subcommittee's members or hold electronic forums. Meetings and forums should be coordinated with the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy. A portion of the meeting may be restricted to regular members of the subcommittee or their alternates in order to deal, inter alia, with changes of membership and election of officers. Minutes of meetings will be communicated to the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy and published using appropriate means [see Article 4(d)].</p>	<p>elected to a Subcommittee at any time by a vote of the existing regular members." had been kept. But shouldn't voting on new members be part of the "administrative workings of the Subcommittee"? What other "administrative workings" are there for which the rights of regular and co-opted members of a Subcommittee should differ? This does not seem to be clear from the text. The addition clarifies this.</p> <p>Online meetings are now routine and easily organized so it seems appropriate to encourage meetings more frequently.</p> <p>Clarification on the handling of minutes in line with the proposed amendment to Article 4(d).</p>
<p>U</p>	<p>(5) Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall work within the framework provided by the International</p>	<p>(5) Subcommittees on Taxonomy, which focus on particular taxa, shall work within the framework</p>	<p>Clarification of the difference to Ad Hoc Subcommittees.</p>

	<p>Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP) in order to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Encourage and undertake research on the evolutionary relationships among the organisms in the taxa under study. (b) Evaluate and make recommendations regarding characters or procedures useful in distinguishing the organisms and taxa under study. (c) Make recommendations regarding classification of the organisms in the taxa under study. A Subcommittee on Taxonomy cannot legislate on classification but may contribute materially towards the general acceptance of a classification. (d) Make recommendations to the JC regarding nomenclature for the organisms in the taxa under study, including recommendations for the conservation or rejection of names. (e) Offer advice on recognition of the nomenclatural types of various taxa. (f) Make recommendations regarding emendations of the ICNP. (g) Recommend minimal standards for the description of new taxa. Such recommendations shall include a list of characters and procedures for their assessment and shall be reviewed at regular intervals. The standards shall be published in the IJSEM and/or other microbiological journals. They shall be minimal and in no way limit the extent of investigation or 	<p>provided by the ICNP to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Encourage and undertake research on the evolutionary relationships among the organisms in the taxa under study. (b) Evaluate and make recommendations regarding characters or procedures useful in distinguishing the organisms and taxa under study. (c) Make recommendations regarding classification of the organisms in the taxa under study. A Subcommittee on Taxonomy cannot legislate on classification but may contribute materially towards the general acceptance of a classification. (d) Make recommendations to the JC regarding nomenclature for the organisms in the taxa under study, including recommendations for the conservation or rejection of names. (e) Offer advice on recognition of the nomenclatural types of various taxa. (f) Recommend minimal standards for the description of new taxa. Such recommendations shall include a list of characters and procedures for their assessment and shall be reviewed at regular intervals. The standards shall be published in the IJSEM and/or other microbiological journals. Such standards shall be minimal and in no way limit the extent of investigation or 	<p>Any interested party can do this as per Article 13.2 so it need not be designated as a specific function of the Subcommittees.</p>
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	<p>contravene Principle 1 (4) of the ICNP.</p> <p>(h) Maintain a list of validly published and other names that have been applied to the organisms in the taxa under study.</p> <p>(i) While statements relating to such studies and recommendations may appear in subcommittee minutes, they may also be submitted separately for publication in the IJSEM.</p>	<p>contravene Principle 1(4) of the ICNP.</p> <p>(g) Maintain a list of validly published and other names that have been applied to the organisms in the taxa under study.</p> <p>(h) Include statements and recommendations relating to the above studies in Subcommittee minutes or submit them separately for publication in the IJSEM or elsewhere, as appropriate [Article 4(d)].</p> <p>(6) Ad Hoc Subcommittees, which focus on an overarching nomenclature-related topic, shall work within the framework provided by the ICNP to:</p> <p>(a) Evaluate and make recommendations regarding the overarching nomenclature-related topic that is their remit, as approved by the Executive Board.</p> <p>(b) Cooperate with other committees or similar bodies appointed to consider problems related to the overarching nomenclature-related topic.</p> <p>(c) Make recommendations regarding emendations of the ICNP.</p> <p>(d) Publish recommendations for addressing the overarching nomenclature-related topic in the IJSEM and/or other microbiological journals.</p>	<p>This is where the new clauses begin to formalize the role of Ad Hoc Subcommittees.</p> <p>In contrast to the comment above (regarding deleted article 5.f), this is included here as Ad Hoc Subcommittees may be formed to do exactly this.</p>
<p>U</p>	<p>(c) Dissolution of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy.</p> <p>(1) Subcommittees on Taxonomy may be dissolved if the members no longer consider that their work is required. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be informed.</p> <p>(2) Subcommittees on Taxonomy that have not</p>	<p>(c) Dissolution of a Subcommittee on Taxonomy or an Ad Hoc Subcommittee.</p> <p>(1) Subcommittees on Taxonomy and Ad Hoc Subcommittees may dissolve themselves if the members no longer consider that their work is required. The Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy shall be informed.</p> <p>(2) Subcommittees that have not produced minutes</p>	<p>Additions in line with the formalisation of the role of Ad Hoc Subcommittees.</p>

	<p>produced minutes over a five-year period will be considered inactive and dissolved by action of the EB-ICSP if no Chair, Secretary or members can be identified to continue the work.</p>	<p>over a five-year period will be considered inactive and dissolved by action of the EB-ICSP if no Chair, Secretary or members can be identified to continue the work.</p> <p>(3) Ad Hoc Subcommittees will report regularly to the EB-ICSP via the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy and, if appropriate, using other means [see Article 4(d)] until completion of their remit, at which point a summary report will be prepared for submission to the ICSP and, if appropriate, publication in IJSEM or on other suitable platforms [see Article 4(d)].</p>	
<p>P</p>	<p>Article 7</p> <p>The Judicial Commission</p> <p>(a) Functions of the Judicial Commission. The Judicial Commission (JC) is a subsidiary of the ICSP and has the following functions:</p> <p>(1) To provide the ICSP expert advice on the interpretation of the ICNP, Requests for Opinions, and other matters requested of it.</p> <p>(2) To consider all Requests for Opinions relative to the interpretation of the ICNP. An Opinion shall be issued when seven or more Commissioners vote in favour of issuance. All Opinions shall be submitted to the ICSP for approval.</p>	<p>Article 7</p> <p>The Judicial Commission</p> <p>(a) Functions of the Judicial Commission. The Judicial Commission (JC) is a subsidiary of the ICSP and has the following functions:</p> <p>(1) To provide the ICSP expert advice on the interpretation of the ICNP, Requests for Opinions, and other matters requested of it. To publish guidelines on the interpretation of the ICNP as deemed necessary.</p> <p>(2) To consider all Requests for Opinions relative to the interpretation of the ICNP [see Article 8]. An action of the JC, such as the rejection or conservation of a name, shall only be issued when a majority of the Commissioners vote in favour. A tied vote is resolved by the vote of the three officers of the JC.</p>	<p>This formalizes the recent publication of the first Judicial Commission Guidelines; https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.005782</p> <p>Changes are proposed to implement separation of powers between legislature (voting members) and judiciary (JC) and to reduce bureaucracy. Further adaptations regarding the processing of Requests for</p>

	<p>(3) To consider proposals for emendation of the ICNP and make recommendations to the ICSP.</p> <p>(4) To hold such sessions and electronic meetings as may be necessary to transact business.</p> <p>(5) To report to the EB-ICSP the names of all Commissioners whose terms of service will expire and a list of other vacancies in the membership of the Commission.</p> <p>(6) To cooperate with other Commissions or similar bodies appointed to consider problems of nomenclature.</p> <p>(7) To consider recommendations from Subcommittees on Taxonomy or other specialists for the acceptance of lists of names as validly published and applicable to recognizable taxa.</p>	<p>(3) To consider proposals for emendation of the ICNP and make recommendations to the ICSP. As a minimum, this should include an assessment of possible unintended retroactivity, ambiguity and logical inconsistencies (internal and external) of the proposed changes.</p> <p>(4) To hold such sessions and electronic meetings as may be necessary to transact business.</p> <p>(5) To report to the EB-ICSP the names of all Commissioners whose terms of service will expire or any other vacancies in the membership of the Commission (e.g., due to resignation).</p> <p>(6) To cooperate with other commissions or similar bodies appointed to consider problems of nomenclature.</p> <p>7) To consider enquiries from the wider scientific community on matters related to interpretation of the ICNP, particularly in regard to status of names as validly published or otherwise.</p>	<p>an Opinion depend on that. Change proposed to clarify how to proceed in the rare event of a tied vote.</p> <p>Clarification of the focus of the JC when evaluating proposed ICNP emendations.</p> <p>Clarifies when vacancies may occur.</p> <p>Broadens out the constituency from which enquiries may be received.</p>
P	<p>(b) Organization. The Judicial Commission (JC) shall consist of 12 commissioners elected by the members of the ICSP. No member of the JC may serve as a voting member of the EB-ICSP, and members of EB-ICSP may not serve on the JC.</p>	<p>(b) Organization. The Judicial Commission (JC) shall consist of up to 12 and no less than 9 commissioners elected by the members of the ICSP. No member of the JC may serve as a voting member of the ICSP, and voting members of ICSP may not serve on the JC. This restriction is not retroactive.</p>	<p>This clarifies the minimum size of the JC in addition to the target size. It may not always be possible to find an immediate replacement for a resigning Commissioner. Twelve commissioners remains the target. This addition is one of the</p>

<p>(1) Commissioners are nominated by the members of the ICSP and elected to serve in three classes of four Commissioners, one class retiring upon the election of a new class. The terms of classes will begin on 1 September 2020 and every three years thereafter. Members of retiring classes are eligible for re-election.</p> <p>(2) Immediately following the election of each new class of Commissioners, the Chair of the ICSP will organize the election of the officers of the JC from among its members. The officers will include the Chair, Vice-Chair and Secretary. The officers will serve until 1 September 2020 and every three years thereafter but may be reelected if their terms as commissioners have not expired.</p> <p>(3) In the case of resignation or death of a Commissioner between elections, the vacancy is filled by ballot of the members of the ICSP. A Commissioner of one class is eligible for election to a vacancy occurring in another class, but may only be a member of one class. Commissioners elected to fill a vacancy caused by resignation or death shall serve for the unexpired term of the vacancy.</p> <p>(4) If any Commissioner cannot attend the meetings of the Judicial Commission, an</p>	<p>(1) Commissioners are elected by the members of the ICSP to serve in three classes of four or three Commissioners, one class retiring upon the election of a new class. A nomination for election requires the written support of at least one Full Member of the ICSP and should summarise the relevant expertise of the candidate. The terms of classes begin on 1 September 2020 and every three years thereafter. Members of retiring classes are eligible for re-election.</p> <p>(2) Immediately following the election of each new class of Commissioners, the Chair of the ICSP will organize the election of the officers of the JC from among its members. The officers will include the Chair, Vice-Chair and Secretary. The officers serve until 1 September 2020 and every three years thereafter but may be re-elected if their terms as commissioners have not expired.</p> <p>(3) In the case of resignation, removal from office or death of a Commissioner between elections, the vacancy is filled by ballot of the members of the ICSP. A Commissioner of one class is eligible for election to a vacancy occurring in another class but may only be a member of one class. Commissioners elected to fill a vacancy caused by resignation, removal from office or death shall serve for the unexpired term of the vacancy.</p>	<p>pillars to implement the separation of powers been the legislature and the judiciary.</p> <p>This addition clarifies the process for nominating a potential commissioner for election.</p> <p>This addition reflects the possibility of removal from office under Article 17 (formerly Article 18), and it clarifies the minimum size of the JC.</p> <p>As above, alternates are not required now the JC is</p>
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	<p>Alternate having all the rights of a Commissioner except in the election of officers can be chosen.</p> <p>(a) The Commissioner shall name an Alternate from the Full and Co-opted Members of the ICSP.</p> <p>(b) If no name is submitted by the Commissioner, the JC may name an Alternate from the Full and Co-opted Members of the ICSP.</p> <p>(c) No Alternate shall represent more than one absent Commissioner.</p>		<p>meeting regularly via electronic forums.</p>
M	<p>(c) Duties of the Chair of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To preside at meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(2) To prepare in collaboration with the Vice-Chair the agenda for meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(3) To participate in regular meetings of the EB-ICSP as a nonvoting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP.</p> <p>(4) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP.</p> <p>(5) To receive Requests for Opinions submitted to the IJSEM and, if applicable, to transmit these through the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy to appropriate Subcommittees on Taxonomy.</p> <p>(6) To organize the JC's review of Requests for Opinions and Emendation of the ICNP as described below.</p> <p>(7) To represent the JC on such International Committees, Boards or Commissions as may be organized to consider cooperation in biology in</p>	<p>(c) Duties of the Chair of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To preside at meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(2) To prepare in collaboration with the Vice-Chair the agenda for meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(3) To participate in regular meetings of the EB-ICSP as a non-voting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP [see Article 4(d)].</p> <p>(4) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP [see Article 13].</p> <p>(5) To receive Requests for Opinion accepted for publication in the IJSEM from its Editor-in-Chief, and to immediately transmit these to the JC for consideration.</p> <p>(6) To organize the JC's consideration of Requests for Opinions [see Article 8] and recommendations regarding proposals for emendation of the ICNP [see Article 7(3)].</p> <p>(7) To represent the JC on such international committees, boards or commissions as may be organized to consider cooperation in biology in the</p>	<p>Changes intended to clarify the role of the chair and to adapt the wording to current practice. Some changes for clarifying the connection to other Articles.</p>

	<p>the solution of common problems of nomenclature and taxonomy, particularly to work with other similar Commissions or Executive Committees organized for action on problems on nomenclature in other biological sciences.</p> <p>(8) To undertake such other duties as may from time to time be requested by the JC or the ICSP.</p>	<p>solution of common problems of nomenclature and taxonomy, particularly to work with other similar commissions or executive committees organized for action on problems on nomenclature in other biological sciences.</p> <p>(8) To undertake such other duties as may from time to time be requested by the JC or the ICSP.</p>	
M	<p>(d) Duties of the Vice-Chair of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To preside at meetings of the JC in the absence of the Chair. If both the Chair and the Vice-Chair are absent, the commissioners may elect an ad hoc Chair to preside at the meeting.</p> <p>(2) To assume all the duties of the Chair in the event of death or resignation of the Chair, until such time as a new Chair has been elected.</p> <p>(3) To prepare in collaboration with the Chair and the Secretary of JC the agenda for meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(4) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP.</p> <p>(5) To participate in regular meetings of the EB-ICSP as a nonvoting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP.</p> <p>(6) To undertake such other duties as may from time to time be requested by the JC or the ICSP.</p>	<p>(d) Duties of the Vice-Chair of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To preside at meetings of the JC in the absence of the Chair. If both the Chair and the Vice-Chair are absent, the commissioners may elect an ad hoc Chair to preside at the meeting.</p> <p>(2) To assume all the duties of the Chair in the event of death or resignation of the Chair, until such time as a new Chair has been elected.</p> <p>(3) To prepare in collaboration with the Chair and the Secretary of JC the agenda for meetings of the JC.</p> <p>(4) To serve on the Editorial Board for the ICNP [see Article 13].</p> <p>(5) To participate in regular meetings of the EB-ICSP as a non-voting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP [see Article 4(d)].</p> <p>(6) To undertake such other duties as may from time to time be requested by the JC or the ICSP.</p>	<p>Changes intended to clarify the connection to other Articles.</p>
M	<p>(e) Duties of the Secretary of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To prepare and submit copies of the minutes of meetings of the JC for publication in the IJSEM.</p>	<p>(e) Duties of the Secretary of the Judicial Commission</p> <p>(1) To prepare and submit copies of the minutes of meetings of the JC for publication in the appropriate forum [see Article 4(d)].</p>	<p>Changes intended to clarify the connection to other</p>

	<p>(2) Co-ordinate voting by members of the JC and record the outcome of all votes.</p> <p>(3) To participate in regular meetings of the EBICSP as a nonvoting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP.</p>	<p>(2) To co-ordinate voting by members of the JC and to record the outcome of all votes.</p> <p>(3) To participate in regular meetings of the EB-ICSP as a non-voting member to communicate relevant matters regarding the JC and ICSP [see Article 4(d)].</p>	Articles.
P	<p>Article 8</p> <p>Requests for Opinions</p> <p>When directed by the ICNP to seek the consent of the JC or when necessary to resolve differences in opinion regarding the interpretation of the ICNP, the Opinion of the JC may be requested.</p> <p>(a) The first step in the Request for Opinion is submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting the opinion and providing the rationale.</p> <p>(b) As deemed necessary, the Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by members of the JC, the relevant Subcommittee of Taxonomy, and/or ad hoc reviewers. If the manuscript is recommended for publication, the Editor-in-Chief will ensure that the request is communicated to the Chair of the JC for consideration.</p>	<p>Article 8</p> <p>Requests for Opinions</p> <p>When necessary to resolve differences in opinion regarding the interpretation of the ICNP or when necessary to clarify other questions regarding the nomenclature of prokaryotes, the opinion of the JC may be requested.</p> <p>(a) The first step in the Request for an Opinion is submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting the opinion and providing the rationale.</p> <p>(b) The Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by members of the JC and, if deemed necessary, by members of the relevant Subcommittee on Taxonomy, and/or ad hoc reviewers. IJSEM peer review does not antedate an Opinion of the JC but the manuscript should be rejected if it:</p> <p>(1) fails to adequately present its case within the framework and appropriate application of the ICNP.</p> <p>(2) revisits a previously denied Request for an Opinion without presenting significant new information on the case.</p> <p>(3) requests the reconsideration of a previously issued Judicial Opinion but neither presents new evidence nor a new rationale.</p>	Additional text clarifies the circumstances under which a Request for an Opinion may not be published in IJSEM

<p>(c) If the manuscript is rejected upon review, seven members of the ICSP may request that the Request for Opinion proceeds further. In this case, the proposal is published in the IJSEM with a note identifying the members who support its publication.</p> <p>(d) The proposal will then be reviewed by the JC within six months of publication. If approved by seven or more Commissioners, the proposal shall be submitted to the members of the ICSP for further consideration.</p> <p>(e) If not approved by the JC, the reasons for rejection will be communicated to the ICSP and the authors of the Request for Opinion.</p> <p>(f) The authors will then have three months to appeal the decision to the JC. If the JC now approves the Request for Opinion, it will be submitted to the ICSP along with the explanation for the initial rejection and the appeal.</p> <p>(g) If the JC does not approve the Request for Opinion upon appeal, the authors may appeal directly to the ICSP within three months of the second rejection. In this case, they should communicate to the Executive Secretary the original Request for Opinion, the reasons for rejection by the JC, and the basis for appeal.</p>	<p>If the manuscript is accepted for publication, the Editor-in-Chief will ensure that the request is communicated to the Chair of the JC for consideration immediately upon acceptance (i.e. in preprint or 'author accepted manuscript' form).</p> <p>(c) If the manuscript is rejected upon review, seven voting members of the ICSP may request that the Request for Opinion proceed further. In this case, the proposal is published in the IJSEM with a note identifying the members who support its publication.</p> <p>(d) The proposal will then be processed by the JC within six months of publication in the IJSEM. If approved by a majority of the Commissioners, the Judicial Opinion shall be submitted to the IJSEM for publication. JC ballots should not have abstention as an option.</p> <p>(e) Each Judicial Opinion must describe the reasons for granting or denying the Request for an Opinion, or parts thereof. The rationale presented therein must be related to the pertinent clauses of the ICNP and, if applicable, to previous publications of the JC. Commissioners who disagree with the majority vote on the Judicial Opinion may include a minority report alongside the main Judicial Opinion.</p> <p>(f) Decisions of the Judicial Commission may be overturned in a subsequent Judicial Opinion.</p>	<p>Clarification of the voting process. Removing abstentions is one of the measures to reduce the probability of a tied vote. Judges cannot abstain either.</p> <p>As mentioned above, the need for Judicial Opinions to be approved by the voting members of the ICSP is questionable. In order to properly implement the separation of powers and to reduce the amount of bureaucracy, the processing of an RfaO is proposed here to be radically simplified.</p> <p>Text in (e) - (g) in the older version is a rather cumbersome process in that it gives authors of RfaO two</p>
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	<p>(h) The ICSP will make its decision within six months, which will be final. Notification of the decision shall be published in the IJSEM.</p> <p>(i) In the absence of an opinion by the JC within one year of the publication of the Request for Opinion, the matter will be transferred to the ICSP for a final decision. The JC will submit all correspondence on the matter to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP, who will arrange for the discussion and vote either by electronic means or at a plenary meeting within six months.</p>	<p>(g) In the absence of the submission of an Opinion for publication by the JC within half a year of the publication of the Request for an Opinion, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP shall reprimand the JC for the delay. In the absence of the submission of an Opinion for publication by the JC within one year of the publication of the Request for an Opinion, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP shall initiate an investigation by the EB-ICSP into the removal of members of the JC from office [see Article 17].</p>	<p>separate opportunities to contest the decision of the JC. Moreover, the Statutes have unfairly favoured the authors of a RfaO, failing to consider that the interests of third parties may also be affected by a Judicial Opinion. The new version is much simpler, whilst still protecting the 'right to reply' of the author(s) of RfaO and of any third party.</p> <p>The new version also enforces much greater procedural and textual transparency in the Judicial Opinions themselves.</p>
M	<p>Article 9</p> <p>Publications Committee</p> <p>(a) The members of the Publications Committee shall be the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP, the Chair and Vice-Chair of the JC, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP, the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, and the Editor-in-Chiefs of the publications authorized by the ICSP.</p> <p>(1) The Vice-Chair of the ICSP shall be Chair of the</p>	<p>Article 9</p> <p>Publications Committee</p> <p>(a) The members of the Publications Committee shall be the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP, the Chair and Vice-Chair of the JC, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP, the Secretary for Subcommittees on Taxonomy, and the Editor-in-Chiefs of the publications authorized by the ICSP. The Publisher of the IJSEM is entitled to send an ex officio delegate to the Publications Committee.</p> <p>(1) The Vice-Chair of the ICSP shall be Chair of the</p>	<p>This addition reflects the terms of the current publishing agreement between ICSP and Microbiology Society (publisher of IJSEM).</p>

	<p>Publications Committee.</p> <p>(2) The Executive Secretary shall be Secretary of the Publications Committee.</p> <p>(3) Should a conflict of interest arise for any member of the Publications Committee, an alternate will be appointed from full members of the ICSP by the remaining members of the Committee.</p> <p>(b) The functions of the Publications Committee shall be the following.</p> <p>(1) Make recommendations to the ICSP for the establishment of such publications as deemed necessary for the advancement of the systematics of prokaryotes and their Editorial Boards.</p> <p>(2) Be responsible for the publication of the <i>International Journal of Systematics and Evolutionary Microbiology</i> (IJSEM), <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes</i> (ICNP), the <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> and the "Statutes of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes".</p> <p>(3) Prepare an Annual Report and Financial Statement relating to publications for transmission to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP and the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(4) Submit a Report of the Publications Committee through the Executive Secretary of the ICSP for transmission to ICSP at each plenary meeting.</p>	<p>Publications Committee.</p> <p>(2) The Executive Secretary shall be Secretary of the Publications Committee.</p> <p>(3) Should a conflict of interest arise for any member of the Publications Committee, an alternate will be appointed from full members of the ICSP by the remaining members of the Committee.</p> <p>(b) The functions of the Publications Committee shall be the following.</p> <p>(1) Make recommendations to the ICSP for the establishment of such publications as deemed necessary for the advancement of the systematics of prokaryotes and their Editorial Boards.</p> <p>(2) Be responsible for the publication of the <i>International Journal of Systematics and Evolutionary Microbiology</i> (IJSEM), <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes</i> (ICNP), the <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> and the "Statutes of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes".</p> <p>(3) To receive an annual report, including a financial statement from audited accounts, from the Publisher regarding the publication of IJSEM and to report on this to the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(4) Submit a Report of the Publications Committee through the Executive Secretary of the ICSP for transmission to ICSP at each plenary meeting.</p>	<p>Change better reflects the reporting arrangements in the current publishing agreement between ICSP and Microbiology Society.</p>
-	Article 10	Article 10	

	The official publications of the ICSP are the IJSEM (formerly <i>International Journal of Systematic Bacteriology</i>), ICNP (formerly <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Bacteria</i>), "Statutes of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes", and <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> .	The official publications of the ICSP are the IJSEM (formerly <i>International Journal of Systematic Bacteriology</i>), ICNP (formerly <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Bacteria</i>), "Statutes of the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes", and <i>Approved Lists of Bacterial Names</i> .	
-	<p>Article 11</p> <p>Sponsorship of Publications. No publication of the ICSP or any of its organizations shall bear any indication of sponsorship by a commercial company, or institution connected in any way with a commercial company, except an acceptable acknowledgement of financial assistance. In cases of doubt, the EB-ICSP will make the final decision.</p>	<p>Article 11</p> <p>Sponsorship of Publications. No publication of the ICSP or any of its organizations shall bear any indication of sponsorship by a commercial company, or institution connected in any way with a commercial company, except an acceptable acknowledgement of financial assistance. In cases of doubt, the EB-ICSP will make the final decision.</p>	
-	<p>Article 12</p> <p>Editorial Boards. Editorial Boards shall be proposed by the EB-ICSP. Currently two Editorial Boards are recognized:</p> <p>(a) The Editorial Board for the <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP)</i>.</p> <p>(b) The Editorial Board for the <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology (IJSEM)</i>.</p>	<p>Article 12</p> <p>Editorial Boards. Editorial Boards shall be proposed by the EB-ICSP. Currently two Editorial Boards are recognized:</p> <p>(a) The Editorial Board for the <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP)</i>.</p> <p>(b) The Editorial Board for the <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology (IJSEM)</i>.</p>	
M	<p>Article 13</p> <p>Editorial Board for the <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP)</i> shall consist of an</p>	<p>Article 13</p> <p>The Editorial Board for the <i>International Code of Nomenclature of Prokaryotes (ICNP)</i> shall consist of an</p>	

	<p>Editor-in-Chief appointed by the EB-ICSP, the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the JC, and the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP. The Editor-in-Chief shall be the Chair of the Editorial Board. The Board shall have power to co-opt.</p> <p>(a) Duties of Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP. The Editor-in-Chief shall be responsible for the continuing revision of the ICNP, for its editing, and publication. The Editor-in-Chief shall submit the manuscript after approval by the Editorial Board for publication in book form and/or electronic form.</p> <p>(1) To supervise consideration of proposals for emendation by the ICSP after publication in the IJSEM, including distribution of comments from the JC and members of the ICSP to the entire ICSP, and supervision of balloting among the ICSP.</p>	<p>Editor-in-Chief appointed by the EB-ICSP, the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the JC, and the Chair and Vice-Chair of the ICSP. The Editor-in-Chief shall be the Chair of the Editorial Board. The Board shall have power to co-opt.</p> <p>(a) Duties of Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP. The Editor-in-Chief shall be responsible for the continuing revision of the ICNP, for its editing, and its publication. The Editor-in-Chief shall submit the manuscript after approval by the Editorial Board for publication in book form and/or electronic form.</p> <p>(1) To supervise consideration of proposals for emendation by the ICSP after publication in the IJSEM, including distribution of comments from the JC and members of the ICSP to the entire ICSP, and supervision of balloting among the ICSP.</p>	
V	<p>(b) Emendation of the ICNP. The emendation of the Code shall follow this procedure.</p> <p>(1) The first step in the emendation of the ICNP is submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting emendation and providing the rationale.</p> <p>(2) The Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by the ICNP Editorial Board and/or ad hoc reviewers. If the manuscript is recommended for publication, the Editor of IJSEM will ensure that the request for emendation is communicated to the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP, who will supervise its further consideration by the JC and ICSP.</p> <p>(3) If the manuscript is rejected upon review, seven members of the ICSP may request that the proposal for emendation proceed further. In this</p>	<p>(b) Emendation of the ICNP. The emendation of the Code shall follow this procedure.</p> <p>(1) The first step in the emendation of the ICNP is submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting emendation and providing the rationale.</p> <p>(2) The Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by the ICNP Editorial Board and/or ad hoc reviewers. If the manuscript is recommended for publication, the Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will ensure that the request for emendation is communicated to the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP, who will supervise its further consideration by the ICSP and JC.</p> <p>(3) If the manuscript is rejected upon review, seven voting members of the ICSP may request that the proposal for emendation proceed further. In this</p>	

<p>case, the proposal is published in the IJSEM with a note identifying the members of the ICSP supporting it.</p> <p>(4) The JC and members of the ICSP will have six months from the publication in the IJSEM to provide comments to the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP. The authors of the proposal will then have two months to respond to the comments. After that time, the proposal and all comments and responses will be communicated to the members of the ICSP for further consideration.</p> <p>(5) The ICSP will make its decision within three months. If the proposal is not accepted, the authors may appeal the decision in writing within three months of notification of the decision of the ICSP.</p> <p>(6) The ICSP will have three months to consider the</p>	<p>case, the proposal is published in the IJSEM with a note identifying the members of the ICSP supporting it.</p> <p>(4) The members of the ICSP, the JC and other interested parties (including the authors of the proposal), will have three months from the publication in the IJSEM to provide comments to the Editor-in-Chief of the ICNP. The EB-ICSP will decide on the nature of any accompanying public discussion deemed appropriate. The authors of the proposal will then have up to six weeks to respond to the comments. Based on the comments, the authors may present a revised version for approval in place of the published version, but must retain the quintessence of the proposal and explain the changes made. After that time, the proposal and all comments will be communicated to the members of the ICSP for voting.</p> <p>(5) The ICSP will make its decision within six weeks. A summary of the debate and the outcome of the vote will be published in the IJSEM. Emendations take effect from the day of publication.</p> <p>(6) If a proposal is not accepted, the authors or other parties may request the voting members of the ICSP to reconsider its decision by submitting a corresponding manuscript to the IJSEM [see Article 13(b)(1)]. This manuscript should present new evidence and/or a new rationale for supporting the emendation of the ICNP, and/or propose an adapted phrasing that addresses critical comments on the previous proposal(s).</p>	<p>Change better reflects current practice having an open discussion period (e.g., recent use of the Slack platform).</p> <p>Restored based on the discussion on Slack. It was not clear why this was removed. Six weeks is a sensible time period, given the three months for deliberation.</p> <p>Addition highlights that changes are enacted by publication in IJSEM rather than compilation into a new edition of the ICNP.</p> <p>Clarifies when an appeal regarding an ICSP decision is appropriate and the appropriate mechanism.</p>
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	appeal, and its decision will be final.		
M	<p>Article 14</p> <p>Editorial Board for <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology</i>. The Editorial Board shall consist of an Editor-in-Chief appointed by the EB-ICSP, the Vice-Chair of the ICSP, a representative appointed by the Publisher, and the Editors that are appointed as described below. The Editor-in-Chief will be Chair of the Editorial Board and may not serve concurrently as the Chair or Vice-Chair of the ICSP.</p> <p>(a) The functions of the Editorial Board shall include implementation of the ICNP, including the General Considerations, Principles, Rules, Recommendations, and the appropriate aspects of the Appendices, within the IJSEM.</p> <p>(b) The Editorial Board shall also implement recommendations made to it by the ICSP, JC or appropriate ad hoc committees formed by the ICSP to deal with specific matters relating to publications that appear in the journal.</p> <p>(c) Nominations for Editorial Board should be sent to the Editor-in-Chief for consideration. The Editor-in-Chief appoints the Editors subject to the approval of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(d) The Editor-in-Chief shall be responsible for the review, acceptance and rejection of submitted manuscripts and for the supervision of the Editors.</p>	<p>Article 14</p> <p>Editorial Board for <i>International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology</i>. The Editorial Board shall consist of an Editor-in-Chief appointed by the EB-ICSP, the Vice-Chair of the ICSP, a representative appointed by the Publisher, and the Editors that are appointed as described below. The Editor-in-Chief will be Chair of the Editorial Board and may not serve concurrently as the Chair or Vice-Chair of the ICSP.</p> <p>(a) The functions of the Editorial Board shall include implementation of the ICNP, including the General Considerations, Principles, Rules, Recommendations, and the appropriate aspects of the Appendices, within the IJSEM.</p> <p>(b) The Editorial Board shall also implement recommendations made to it by the ICSP, JC or appropriate Ad Hoc Subcommittees formed by the ICSP to deal with specific matters relating to publications that appear in the journal.</p> <p>(c) Nominations for Editorial Board should be sent to the Editor-in-Chief for consideration. The Editor-in-Chief appoints the Editors subject to the approval of the EB-ICSP. If considered necessary, e.g., if an Editor does not perform the functions in a satisfactory way, the Editor-in-Chief may remove an Editor subject to the approval of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(d) The Editor-in-Chief shall be responsible for the review, acceptance and rejection of submitted manuscripts and for the supervision of the Editors.</p>	<p>Addition to clarify the role of Editor-In-Chief.</p>

<p>(e) The Editor-in-Chief and the Editors shall be appointed for terms of up to five years subject to reappointment and earlier termination. Editors may serve for no more than two consecutive terms in any one capacity.</p> <p>(f) Policy matters deemed important by the ICSP shall be communicated through the EB-ICSP to the Editor-in-Chief. Policy matters initiated by the Publisher shall be communicated through the Editor-in-Chief to the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(g) Editorial policy, whether initiated by the ICSP, the Publisher or elsewhere, shall be communicated through the Editor-in-Chief to the Editors.</p> <p>(h) The Editor-in-Chief may serve on the Publisher's editorial policy committee representing the ICSP. The Editor-in-Chief shall act on behalf of the EB-ICSP, except in respect to the negotiation of contracts with the Publisher. In other transactions with the Publisher, the Editor-in-Chief shall forward copies of correspondence immediately to members of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(i) The Publisher will submit all material for publication in the IJSEM to the Editor-in-Chief and Editors. The Editor-in-Chief and Editors shall have the power to refer such submissions to referees for assessment and reject such submissions that are deemed unsuitable for publication, provided that, in such instances, authors shall have the right of appeal via the Chair of the Editorial Board.</p> <p>(j) The EB-ICSP shall be entitled to receive annually such part of the management accounts of the Publisher as relate to publication of the IJSEM and the audited</p>	<p>(e) The Editor-in-Chief and the Editors shall be appointed for terms of up to five years subject to reappointment and earlier termination. Editors may serve for no more than two consecutive terms in any one capacity.</p> <p>(f) Policy matters deemed important by the ICSP shall be communicated through the EB-ICSP to the Editor-in-Chief. Policy matters initiated by the Publisher shall be communicated through the Editor-in-Chief to the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(g) Editorial policy, whether initiated by the ICSP, the Publisher or elsewhere, shall be communicated through the Editor-in-Chief to the Editors.</p> <p>(h) The Editor-in-Chief may serve on the Publisher's editorial policy committee representing the ICSP. The Editor-in-Chief shall act on behalf of the EB-ICSP, except in respect to the negotiation of contracts with the Publisher. In other transactions with the Publisher, the Editor-in-Chief shall forward copies of correspondence immediately to members of the EB-ICSP.</p> <p>(i) The Publisher will submit all material for publication in the IJSEM to the Editor-in-Chief and Editors. The Editor-in-Chief and Editors shall have the power to refer such submissions to referees for assessment and reject such submissions that are deemed unsuitable for publication, provided that, in such instances, authors shall have the right of appeal via the Chair of the Editorial Board.</p> <p>(j) The EB-ICSP shall be entitled to receive annually such part of the management accounts of the Publisher as relate to publication of the IJSEM and the audited</p>	
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	<p>accounts of the Publisher and to have access to such part of the books and records of the Publisher as are relevant to publication of the IJSEM at any time on giving reasonable notice and during normal business hours.</p> <p>(k) Minutes of the Editorial Board meeting will be made available to the EB-ICSP.</p>	<p>accounts of the Publisher and to have access to such part of the books and records of the Publisher as are relevant to publication of the IJSEM at any time on giving reasonable notice and during normal business hours.</p> <p>(k) Minutes of the Editorial Board meeting will be made available to the EB-ICSP.</p>	
M	<p>Article 16</p> <p>No one connected with a commercial firm may use his or her connection with the ICSP or any of its committees, commissions, and organizations, either as a member or officer, to advertise or promote his or her commercial interests in any way. Members of the EB-ICSP, JC, Editor-in-Chief and Editors of the IJSEM and ICNP shall submit a conflict of interest (COI) statement to the Chair of the ICSP upon the time of their appointment and must notify the Chair of any changes in their conflicts of interest during their terms of office.</p>	<p>Article 15</p> <p>No one connected with a commercial firm may use his or her connection with the ICSP or any of its committees, commissions, and organizations, either as a member or officer, to advertise or promote his or her commercial interests in any way. Members of the EB-ICSP, JC, Editor-in-Chief and Editors of the IJSEM and ICNP shall submit a conflict of interest (COI) statement to the Chair of the ICSP upon the time of their appointment and must notify the Chair of any changes in their conflicts of interest during their terms of office.</p>	<p>Renumbered as it was noticed that there is no Article 15 in the current version of the statutes.</p>
M	<p>Article 17</p> <p>Amendments of the Statutes</p> <p>(a) Five or more members of the ICSP may initiate amendment of the Statutes by submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting amendment and providing the rationale.</p>	<p>Article 16</p> <p>Amendments of the Statutes</p> <p>(a) Five or more voting members of the ICSP may initiate amendment of the Statutes by submission of a manuscript to the IJSEM requesting amendment and providing the rationale.</p>	<p>Renumbered.</p>
V	<p>(b) As deemed necessary, the Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by the EB-ICSP and/or ad hoc reviewers. Following the</p>	<p>(b) As deemed necessary, the Editor-in-Chief of the IJSEM will supervise the manuscript's review by members of the EB-ICSP and/or ad hoc reviewers. Following the</p>	<p>Clarification of the procedure. The entire EB-ICSP will hardly review such</p>

	<p>response of the authors to the reviewers' comments and submission of revisions if desired, the Editor-in-Chief will ensure timely publication in IJSEM and communication to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP for consideration by the full membership.</p> <p>(c) The proposal will then be reviewed by the ICSP within six months of publication in the IJSEM, where at least 90 days is provided for deliberation by the members. Approval will require a vote of at least ten Members and shall be reached on the basis of a simple majority of the members voting.</p> <p>(d) Notice of amendments approved by the ICSP shall be published in the IJSEM as a minute of a meeting of the ICSP or EB-ICSP.</p>	<p>response of the authors to the reviewers' comments and submission of revisions if desired, the Editor-in-Chief will ensure timely publication in IJSEM and communication to the Executive Secretary of the ICSP for consideration by the membership.</p> <p>(c) The proposal will then be debated by the ICSP within three months of publication in the IJSEM, and all comments compiled. The authors of the proposal will then have up to six weeks to respond to the comments. Based on the comments, the authors of the proposal may present a revised version for approval in place of the published version, but must retain the essence of the proposal and explain the changes made. After that time, the proposal and all comments will be communicated to the Full Members of the ICSP for voting.</p> <p>(d) The ICSP will make its decision within six weeks. Approval will require a vote of a majority of the members eligible to vote [see Article 2(e)]. Notice of amendments approved by the ICSP shall be published in the IJSEM as minutes of meetings of the ICSP or EB-ICSP.</p>	<p>a manuscript.</p> <p>This adapts the discussion and voting to the one used for proposals to emend the ICNP.</p> <p>Clarifies how to make use of the results from the debate period.</p>
M	<p>Article 18</p> <p>Officers of the ICSP, including members of the Executive Board, the Judicial Commission, and the Subcommittees of Taxonomy may be removed from office by a vote of the members of the ICSP. Reasons for removal from office include failure to perform the responsibilities of the office, using the office for purposes other than those specified in the Statutes, and violation of the conflict of</p>	<p>Article 17</p> <p>Officers of the ICSP, including members of the Executive Board, the Judicial Commission, and the Subcommittees of Taxonomy and Ad Hoc committees may be removed from office by a vote of the Full Members of the ICSP. Reasons for removal from office include failure to perform the responsibilities of the office, using the office for purposes other than those specified in the Statutes, violation of the</p>	<p>Renumbered.</p>

	<p>interest statement.</p> <p>(a) Removal from office is initiated by a letter from five or more members to the Executive Secretary or, if the Secretary is the subject of the complaint, to the Chair of the ICSP. The letter should specify the basis for removal. The officer will then have 30 days to respond. At the end of that time, the proposal to remove and the officer's response will be circulated to the members of the ICSP for a consideration. A vote of two-thirds of ten or more members is necessary to remove an officer.</p>	<p>conflict-of-interest statement, and acting in any other way that significantly contravenes the Statutes.</p> <p>(a) Removal from office is initiated by a letter from five or more Full Members to the Executive Secretary or, if the Secretary is the subject of the complaint, to the Chair of the ICSP. The letter should specify the basis for removal. The officer will then have six weeks to respond. At the end of that time, the proposal to remove and the officer's response will be circulated to the members of the ICSP for a consideration. Decisions to remove an officer require a vote by a majority (i.e., more than 50%) of the members eligible to vote and shall be reached on the basis of a qualified majority of two thirds of those members who vote.</p> <p>(b) A Full Member [Article 2(a)] may be removed on the same grounds as for the removal of officers by the Member Society which appointed the Full Member. A request for removal shall be notified to the Society by the EB-ICSP. If necessary, the matter may be referred to the IUMS Executive Board.</p> <p>(c) Co-opted Members [Article 2(b)] and Life Members [Article 2(c)] may be removed from membership on the same grounds and by the same procedure as for the removal of officers.</p>	<p>Reasons for removal from membership may also apply to Full Members. As these are appointed by IUMS Members Societies, these need to be invoked. In case of otherwise unresolvable issues, the IUMS Executive Board may step in.</p> <p>Removal from office is possible in all cases where the ICSP also appoints those officers. Therefore, it must be possible to revoke the membership of Co-Opted Members and Life Members in exactly the same way.</p>
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Statutes revision proposals

Collated and slightly redacted comments posted on Slack – 10 January – 22 August 2024

Jan. 10 - Aharon Oren

On January 9, 2024, the Executive Board of the ICSP completed the proposals for revision of the Statutes of the ICSP. The proposal was submitted for publication in the IJSEM. Attached you will find a copy of the submitted version ("Supplementary file ...") and a version annotated with additional comments. A six-month public discussion will start on the day the proposal is published in the IJSEM, and will be followed by a ballot. However, the documents are open for discussion already now.

Jan. 10 – Giovanna Felis

"Like"

Jan. 17 – Aharon Oren

I want to start a discussion about the proposed change in Article 2 (c) – Life members – p. 4 of the annotated version. The text proposed, based on the majority of EB members, is: Life Members. The ICSP may appoint to Life Membership of the ICSP **up to four** retired individuals who have rendered distinguished service to the ICSP. To this, Iain Sutcliffe commented: why limit the number of the life members to four? In reality, there has rarely been more than that number but it seems unnecessarily precise. If you are keen to set an upper limit, I would have thought 6 or 7 more prudent.

I do not see any reason why the statutes should limit the numbers of Life Members. We currently have three: Jean Paul Euzeby, Karl-Heinz Schleifer, and George Garrity. I do not expect a large number of proposal for new life members in the coming years. Remember also that a life member cannot be elected as an officer in the EB later, and (unless the statutes will be changed accordingly) he/she may not be able to vote on ICSP matters even if he/she is also happens to be the delegate of a national society. Moreover, if there will be two nominees who are worthy, we should not postpone the approval until one of the current Life Members (to whom I wish a long and happy life) will pass away.

Jan. ... - Markus Göker

It is important to note that the restriction of the number of life members is bound to granting them voting rights. The discussion within the EB-ICSP showed concerns regarding the creation of a kind of house of lords. Please keep in mind that a life member is elected for the persons' entire lifetime. If, however, life members do not get voting rights, no restriction of their number is necessary. Therefore, the idea was to bind these changes together. Recent changes proposed for the ICSP also included measures that were connected to each other and were never intended to be separately implemented. The same holds for other proposed changes to the statutes, i.e. they form connected block that implements the same underlying idea. There should be a sole vote on each such block. ...

Jan. 18 - Iain.sutcliffe

Regarding comments on life members, as someone can only be elected a life member in recognition of having "rendered distinguished service to the ICSP", then inevitably there will

be a very small pool of eligible candidates, hence I don't think it necessary to specify a maximum number and it won't distort the balance of the ICSP to grant them voting rights.

Apr. 5 - Markus Göker

... I would also like to comment on how to deal with alternative proposals made on this platform. Irrespective of the specific content of the proposals for revision of the Statutes, I would like to point out that it would be detrimental if a decision led to a vote with more than two options. For example, if three options are presented (a) keep as is, (b) change to X, (c) change to Y, then there may well be a majority for change, but not a majority for either X or Y. Such a three-way vote would be better presented as two two-way votes (i) change or no change, and (ii) X or Y. However, those who voted for no change in (i) are likely to abstain in (ii). My proposal would therefore be that in all cases where the authors of the proposed revision agree that a particular part of the proposal published in the IJSEM should be replaced by a proposal made here, the former should not be included in the ballot.

As there has been some disagreement in the EB-ICSP on an alternative version we had discussed to the text currently included, this may be the time to consider changing the last sentence of the proposed new 1st paragraph of Article 5 to read as follows: "No member of the EB-ICSP may serve on the Executive Board in any capacity for more than three consecutive terms, or in the same capacity for more than two consecutive terms; after an absence of one term, former members of the EB-ICSP who have served three terms on the Executive Board shall be eligible for re-election as an Officer." What do you think about this? I think the intention of this alternative proposal was clear from our internal debate, but we could not find an unambiguous formulation. Although I think the wording proposed here is sufficiently clear, you may prefer the published version as they differ in content.

For Article 6(b) our paper suggests to delete the phrase "but co-opted members have no voting rights in the administrative workings of the Subcommittee". The intention of this removal is clear. However, the sentence "New members may be elected to a Subcommittee at any time by a vote of the existing regular members." has been kept. But shouldn't voting on new members be part of the "administrative workings of the Subcommittee"? What other "administrative workings" are there for which the rights of regular and co-opted members of a Subcommittee should differ? This does not seem to be clear from the text.

I therefore propose the following wording for Article 6(b) instead: "A Subcommittee shall contain regular members, which are affiliated with a Member Society of the BAM Division of the IUMS. The Subcommittee may co-opt other specialists. New members may be elected to a Subcommittee at any time. Prior to the election of officers [see Article 6(a)], the regular members of the Subcommittee shall decide for the entire term whether only regular members or also co-opted members of the Subcommittee shall be eligible for office and have the right to vote in the election of new members and officers." This gives each Subcommittee the right to determine how it conducts these aspects of its business. I guess almost all Subcommittees will choose the more open version anyway (either explicitly or implicitly). However, as we now also propose Ad Hoc Subcommittees that can theoretically cover all kinds of ICSP-related work, the option of having stricter rules should be provided.

Apr. 7 - Iain Sutcliffe

As Aharon wrote in his post of 10th January "However, the documents are open for discussion already now." I think that relevant comments from the General channel should be copied over here. I think the advantage of having the discussion on the general channel was so all Slack members (116) had ready access to the debate rather than having to electively join a dedicated channel (only 9 so far). However, I agree it is far tidier to have a separate channel.

Apr. 12 - Aharon Oren

Concerning Article 5: I am not sure that the text proposed by Markus ("No member of the EB-ICSP may serve on the Executive Board in any capacity for more than three consecutive terms, or in the same capacity for more than two consecutive terms; after an absence of one term, former members of the EB-ICSP who have served three terms on the Executive Board shall be eligible for re-election as an Officer.") reflects the intention. It was my understanding that an EB member who has served for two consecutive terms in any function cannot be re-elected for any EB function for the next term.

Apr. 12 - Aharon Oren

Markus proposed: "Irrespective of the specific content of the proposals for revision of the Statutes, I would like to point out that it would be detrimental if a decision led to a vote with more than two options. For example, if three options are presented (a) keep as is, (b) change to X, (c) change to Y, then there may well be a majority for change, but not a majority for either X or Y. Such a three-way vote would be better presented as two two-way votes (i) change or no change, and (ii) X or Y. However, those who voted for no change in (i) are likely to abstain in (ii). My proposal would therefore be that in all cases where the authors of the proposed revision agree that a particular part of the proposal published in the IJSEM should be replaced by a proposal made here, the former should not be included in the ballot."

In my opinion this will cause unnecessary complication of the voting procedure and of the ballot form.

Apr. 12 - Markus Göker

Aharon, thanks for your comments. As for Article 5, I was referring to what I perceived to be the intention of those among the authors of our paper who wanted to extend the number of consecutive terms to three. I did not refer to the intentions of the current revision of the Statutes, which restrict everything to two consecutive terms. As for complications of the voting procedure and the ballot form, I think a form that asks "please choose either option A or B" is easier than a form that asks "please choose either option A or B or C ...". In that respect, my suggestion would simplify the voting procedure and the ballot form. It would of course be even simpler to disallow all changes to the proposed revisions of the Statutes. However, as far as I remember, that was not what was discussed.

Aug. 20 – Markus Göker

It seems almost all messages to this channel aren't seen any more because of the Slack policy that on "the free version of Slack, messages and files older than 90 days are hidden". I think we so far have had the following suggestions for changes before putting this to the ballot.

(A) As for the suggestion made earlier to remove the restriction of the number of life

members, it would be interesting whether this was based on the assumption that life members don't have voting rights, as our proposal also includes the idea to give them voting rights.

(B) As for the idea to change the proposal for the 1st paragraph of Article 5, this intends to reflect a previous suggestion by the acting Chairman. This was discussed by the authors but did not make it into the IJSEM paper.

(C) As for the suggested change to proposed Article 6(b), I haven't seen any claims to the contrary on Slack.

As for my insistence that the ballot should not include alternative proposed versions but only the current version of the Statutes and one proposed new version, I think this is the simplest way. It only requires that the authors agree beforehand on what to put to the ballot.

Aug. 20 – Markus Göker

The EB-ICSP has repeatedly and also recently discussed the issue of inactivity, which leads, e.g., to low voter turnout, which looks embarrassing in the minutes and other publications. Therefore, it has been suggested to include this paragraph in the proposal to change the Statutes before putting it to the ballot:

“Article 2(f) **Inactivity**. A Full or Co-opted member of the ICSP shall be considered inactive if (i) the member has not participated in two consecutive, non-overlapping votes in which the member should have participated according to these Statutes, despite a regular call to vote, a regular voting period and a reminder, or (ii) the member has not participated in two consecutive, non-overlapping meetings in which the member should have participated according to these Statutes and has not sent an apology, despite a regular and timely invitation and a reminder. An inactive member shall cease to be a member, but may be reinstated in accordance with Article 2(a) or Article 2(b).”

Aug. 20 – Aharon Oren

Full members are appointed by IUMS member societies, and their membership can be terminated by their society, not by the ICSP Executive Board or by the ICSP plenary.

Aug. 20 – Markus Göker

Not if we include the proposed paragraph in the Statutes!

Aug. 20 – Aharon Oren

In my opinion such an arrangement must be approved by IUMS. Moreover, it is a lot of work to monitor the activity of each member, and in my opinion it is not worth the trouble. We have more important things to deal with.

Aug. 20 – Markus Göker

I presume almost every institution has rules for dealing with inactivity. It is a reasonable thing to care about such issues. The activity we are talking about here is already monitored by the tellers of each ballot and by the authors of meeting minutes. The issue of inactivity reoccurs every few months in the EB-ICSP meetings, based on such data. There wouldn't be much additional work to do. Member societies of IUMS should have an intrinsic interest in appointing members to the ICSP who are actually active, hence I see no problem here. This

particularly holds since according to the above proposal the same delegate could be reappointed by the member society at any time.

Aug. 20 – Aharon Oren

If approved, we need a volunteer to keep track of the activity of each of the (currently) 46 members. I do not intend to waste my time on this.

Aug. 20 – Markus Göker

I see your point. I think it would be possible to appoint someone else to do such things, although this kind of job would have to remain within the EB-ICSP according to Article 5(b).

Aug. 21 – Iain Sutcliffe

I agree with Aharon on this - in my experience, a less draconian approach would be for the ICSP exec to keep a low key watching brief on members who may be inactive and send a reminder as their obligations if deemed necessary.

Aug. 21 - Markus Göker

... which means more effort in the long run.

Aug. 22 – Ed Moore

I think, at this point, that it is not possible for us (EB-ICSP or ICSP) to consider additional proposals to the revision of the Statutes. The current Statutes indicates, "Five or more members of the ICSP may initiate amendment of the statutes by submission of a manuscript to IJSEM requesting amendment and providing the rationale." Even if "five or more members of the ICSP" are found to support Markus' proposal, new proposals added to the revision of the Statutes that was published will not have met the requirement of, "... submission of a manuscript to IJSEM ...".

Therefore, even though I think that the new proposals by Markus have merit (I might quibble about the issue of missing two consecutive votes or three consecutive votes or three votes within a period of five votes, etc.), In any case, at this point, I think that we may NOT consider new additions to the revision of the Statutes that was published in IJSEM. If we want to include consideration of new additions to revisions of the Statutes during the 'deliberation' period, then the Statutes must be amended accordingly, I think, and those proposals submitted for publication in IJSEM, etc. Alternatively, perhaps we could consider the new proposals if all co-authors agreed to the proposals (although, I think this would not be 'according Hoyle').

Aug. 22 - Markus Göker

It is clear from the wording of the Statutes that they do not prohibit modifications of the proposal to amend the Statutes as result of the debate. Ed, you seem to imply that if something is not mentioned in the Statutes it must not be done. This overlooks the contra proferentem principle that is frequently applied in law.

Aug. 22 - Markus Göker

So, as I suggested, if the majority of the authors of the proposal agree to put modifications to the ballot that are discussed here, this can totally be done. There is no support in the

Statutes for your idea that, although it is a result of the discussion process, a proposal cannot be modified before putting it to the ballot.

Aug. 23 - Markus Göker

I think that, given the huge amount of work that needs to be done to get a revision of the Statutes off the ground, it is appropriate not to rush through these issues, as this may lead -- again! -- to a sub-optimal (sometimes ambiguous and therefore confusing) text. Better wording may mean more work now, but it will mean less work in the long run.

I've already found a significant error in the published version. Our IJSEM paper states in the main text that:

"Article 7(a) and elsewhere: the functioning of the Judicial Commission will be changed to allow **full separation of powers** between the legislature and the judiciary, thereby also **simplifying procedures**."

(My emphasis.) However, the published version does not include our proposal to delete this: "Article 3 (e) To consider and vote on any recommendations made by the Judicial Commission in relation to requests for opinions."

This proposed deletion was included in the internal version of 22 December, but is missing from the 30 December version of the Supplementary Table.

This creates a contradiction in our proposal between Article 3(e) and Article 8 and a contradiction between Article 3(e) and the main text published in the IJSEM. Article 8 and the main text clearly indicate that the proposal includes the removal of the need for judicial opinions to be ratified by the voting members of the ICSP. Although there has also been extensive discussion of why separation of powers is a good idea, this is not even the main point here. The main point is that the published proposal contains logical contradictions. But one purpose of the revision is to clarify the Statutes, not to make them more nebulous. Other such contradictions may be lurking in the darkness of the text. So there should be time to examine them carefully. (edited)

Aug. 23 – Ed Moore

I do think that some additional emendations of the Statutes are necessary, i.e., from recent issues that have arisen, demonstrating that the Statutes still have some ambiguous wording. I think these should be addressed, preferably in the current version of the proposed revision, e.g., as Markus is suggesting, or in a later revision. To my mind, the most important points that need to be clarified are concerning the issues of revision of the protocols for amending The ICNP (Article 13 (b)) and also for amending the Statutes of the ICSP (Article 17). As the current rules describe the protocol for amending the Code: (a) publication requesting emendation; (b) a six-month period for the members of the JC and ICSP (other input is not indicated) to provide comments to the EiC; (c) a two-month period for the authors of proposed emendations to respond to comments, which "will be communicated to members of the ICSP (members of the JC and other 'commenters' are not mentioned) for further consideration" (what does "further consideration" actually mean?); (d) a three-month period for the ICSP to "make its decision", i.e., to vote (is 3-months really necessary to vote on an emendation of The Code? This protocol is needlessly long and laborious. Can we consider to streamline the process? The wording is also sometimes confusing. I suggest that this text should finally codify specific points that seem to be informally implemented. Specifically, the issue of how to deal with "comments to the EiC" from the 6-month 'deliberation' period. As Markus points out above, the process should be able to implement

comments on the emendation that may improve or clarify the published proposed emendation. Should such modifications arising from the deliberations be allowed to change the published proposed emendation? We have allowed such changes in published proposed emendations (with consent of the authors), in some past cases. But, it is not stipulated in the Statutes and, therefore, a potential issue of controversy. We are facing some different, but similar types of issues for amending the Statutes. Besides some 'cleaning up' of some of the text

Aug. 23 – Ed Moore

For consideration of comments to published proposals to amend the Code, I suggest relatively simple emendations to Article 13 (b): [Changes to published proposals for amending the ICNP will be allowed to be submitted to the ICSP for voting for the following reasons: 1) minor corrections or modifications that do not change the core meaning of the published emendation, e.g., spelling, grammar, etc., i.e., with the approval of the author; 2) minor or significant changes that clarify or improve the published proposal, i.e., with the approval of the author.] Besides some 'cleaning up' of text, similar emendations should be proposed for Article 17 of the Statutes. These issues should be discussed at an EB-ICSP meeting.

Aug. 23 - Markus Göker

I generally agree with Ed's comments. Clarifying such ambiguities in the text may create more work now but will result in less work in the long run.

Aug. 29 – Markus Göker

I suggest adding to Article 7(a)(3) a 2nd sentence, resulting in:

"(3) To consider proposals for emendation of the ICNP and make recommendations to the ICSP. As a minimum, this should include an assessment of possible unintended retroactivity, ambiguity and logical inconsistencies (internal and external) of the proposed changes."

These are the issues most suitable for the JC to comment on. Ambiguity and logical inconsistency will most likely make the work of the JC harder, while unintended retroactivity is of general concern. There were situations in the past, as, e.g., in the case of class names made illegitimate, that were due to unintended retroactivity.

Aug. 1. Meng-Syun Li

Dear all, in order to give more flexibility to the JC, I suggest considering an alternative version of the proposed Article 8 (d) and (g):(d) The proposal will then be processed by the JC within six months of publication in the IJSEM. If approved by a majority of the Commissioners, the draft Judicial Opinion shall be submitted to the IJSEM for publication. JC ballots should not have abstention as an option. **If the authors of the Request for an Opinion agree, time for the JC's consideration may be extended by no more than six months.**(g) In the absence of the submission of an Opinion for publication by the JC within half a year of the publication of the Request for an Opinion **and without an extension of time agreed by the authors**, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP shall reprimand the JC for the delay. In the absence of the submission of an Opinion for publication by the JC within one year of the publication of the Request for an Opinion, the Executive Secretary of the ICSP shall initiate an investigation by the EB-ICSP into the removal of members of the JC from office [see Article 17].I think sometimes there is no rush for the authors to receive the

outcome of their Request. So if the authors agree, why not an extension of time for consideration?

Sept. 2 - Reply – Markus Göker

Thanks. The authors will try to provide a revised proposal for amending the Statutes. This suggestion will be discussed.

Sept. 2 - Meng-Syun Li

Also, I would like to highlight that there may be a need to add the mechanism of recusal into the operation of the JC. Judges cannot abstain, but they should definitely be removed from voting if there is a conflict of interest (e.g., being an author of a Request). I think for avoiding a tied vote it is indeed a right call to remove abstention from options in JC ballots. But if abstention is removed and a JC commissioner happens to be an author of a Request, he or she would be forced to vote on his or her own Request, which is quite weird as we are going to call the JC a judiciary. One may opine that nobody would be left to write the Opinion if the entire JC writes a Request. However, I think this would be a very rare case. And what if after abstention the voting is done by only a few commissioners? I think appointing an ad hoc commissioner by the EB-ICSP or ICSP could be an option.

Sept. 2 - Markus Göker

If you allow abstentions, there may be tied votes. If there is a tied vote, a Judicial Opinion cannot be published. Writing a good Opinion requires some knowledge of the Code. To be a good Commissioner, you need even more knowledge of the Code. It is therefore a reasonable scenario for a Commissioner to also be the author of a Request for an Opinion. The limiting factor in the JC is finding a capable and willing author. The same applies to Requests for Opinion. Let's not punish the able and willing by treating them as biased. After all, these are neither criminal proceedings nor court cases, although the analogy of the JC to a court is obvious. The proposed emendation of the Statutes also places more explicit limits on what the JC can do in a Judicial Opinion. If the author of a Request for an Opinion couldn't vote on it even though he was a Commissioner, then the voting members of the ICSP shouldn't vote on their own proposals to emend the ICNP.

Sept. 2 - Meng-Syun Li

Perhaps one could still participate in writing and being the author of an Opinion even if he or she doesn't vote. And I think it is OK for the voting members of the ICSP to vote on their own proposals, because the ICSP functions as a legislature, not judiciary. I made this comment merely for a reminder, and the work of the able and willing is definitely deeply appreciated.

Aug. 30 – Stephen On

I have a couple of questions regarding Article 6 that concerns subcommittees. In the original version, Article 6 (5f) states Subcommittees may "make recommendations regarding emendations of the ICNP". This is omitted from the new proposed version. Why? There is no reason to omit this clause. Subcommittee members are surely as entitled to make recommendations as anyone else, which could I suppose be argued as a justification for omission - having said that, retaining that sentence perhaps alerts

subcommittee members to another activity they may be well placed to consider. I am in favour of retaining this clause for the new proposal.

Aug. 30 – Stephen On

I also seek clarification for Article 6 (5d) which I must admit I have not noticed before. There is something of a conflict I feel between Article 6 (5c) and 6 (5d), in that the latter infers that the only mechanism for a Subcommittee to make recommendations for wider adoption is via the JC, but 6 (5c) states recommendations can be made in other ways. Indeed, a while ago "my" subcommittee did exactly that: Vandamme and On 2001. doi: 10.1099/00207713-51-2-719. I presume both avenues are still valid?

Sept. 4 – M. Göker

I also seek clarification for Article 6 (5d) which I must admit I have not noticed before. There is something of a conflict I feel between Article 6 (5c) and 6 (5d), in that the latter infers that the only mechanism for a Subcommittee to make recommendations for wider adoption is via the JC, but 6 (5c) states recommendations can be made in other ways. Indeed, a while ago "my" subcommittee did exactly that: Vandamme and On 2001. doi: 10.1099/00207713-51-2-719. I presume both avenues are still valid?

If you want to involve the JC, write a Request for an Opinion. Regulated elsewhere. If you want to emend the ICNP, write a proposal to emend the ICNP. Also regulated elsewhere. There is no special path for Subcommittees for these two kinds of requests, nor is one needed.

Sept. 4 - Markus Göker

It is also not clear to me what the conflict between 6(5)(c) and 6(5)(d) is supposed to be. One is about classification, so no need to involve the JC, the other one about nomenclature, hence the need to involve the JC.

Sept. 4 Markus Göker

Also, I would like to highlight that there may be a need to add the mechanism of recusal into the operation of the JC. Judges cannot abstain, but they should definitely be removed from voting if there is a conflict of interest (e.g., being an author of a Request). ...

The point is that the Statutes never envisaged the need for commissioners to abstain when voting on their own Requests for an Opinion. Therefore, removing abstentions entirely from JC decisions would not change this situation. Moreover, the current Statutes put affected third parties at a disadvantage compared to the authors of a Request for an Opinion, because only the latter have a right to appeal under certain circumstances. The proposed emendation of the Statutes would remove this bias.